

GENCHRON: NETWORK ANALYTICS FOR MEDIEVAL LITERATURE STUDIES

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Abstract

Traditional methodologies in historical analysis have often marginalized the contributions of women, resulting in an incomplete understanding of social structures in historical chronicles. This research addresses this gap by developing and applying visual analytics tools to highlight gendered networks within historical chronicles, particularly from the late antique and early medieval periods. The primary objectives of this study are to design a novel visual analytics tool that emphasizes gendered interactions, assess the impact of design choices on data interpretation, and evaluate the challenges and limitations inherent in using such tools for historical analysis.

To achieve these goals, the Genchron: Network Visualizer was developed using React.js and Cytoscape.js. This tool allows for dynamic, real-time manipulation of network visualisations, providing a platform for historians to explore gender dynamics with greater depth and flexibility. The study also conducted a comparative analysis of existing tools highlighting the unique contributions of Genchron in facilitating a more nuanced analysis of gendered interactions.

The results demonstrated that Genchron significantly enhances the ability to analyze complex gendered networks, offering insights that challenge traditional historical narratives. The tool's design, which emphasizes interactivity and user control, was shown to be particularly effective in uncovering the roles of women within these networks. However, the study also identified several challenges, including data quality issues and the need for interdisciplinary collaboration to accurately interpret the visualisations.

In conclusion, this research contributes to the field of Historical Social Network Analysis (HSNA) and digital humanities by providing a novel tool that not only advances the methodological framework for gender analysis but also paves the way for future research into the social structures of the past. The findings suggest that tools like Genchron are essential for creating a more inclusive and accurate portrayal of historical narratives, particularly in the representation of marginalized groups such as women.

Declaration

I confirm that, except where indicated through the proper use of citations and references, this is my original work and that I have not submitted it for any other course or degree.

Signed: _____

Somyajit Chakraborty
September 2, 2024

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Dedication

I dedicate this work to all the incredible women in my life - *Yanrong, Apu, Ma* and *Thamma* who have inspired me to take this project.

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List of Abbreviations

SNA	Social Network Analysis
HSNA	Historical Social Network Analysis
DH	Digital Humanities
WS	Watts-Strogatz (network model)
ER	Erdős-Rényi (network model)
BA	Barabási-Albert (network model)
GIS	Geographic Information Systems
CCL	Connected Component Labeling
DFS	Depth-First Search
BFS	Breadth-First Search
subnet	Sub Network
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience

Chapter 1

Introduction

"The relative absence of women from many historical sources is a reflection not of their insignificance but of the patriarchal frameworks within which these sources were produced. The challenge, therefore, is to develop methodologies that can recover and highlight the roles of women in history, often hidden within the interstices of male-dominated narratives."¹

— Máirín MacCarron, *Bede and Time: Computus, Theology and History in the Early Medieval World* (2019)

Historical chronicles, particularly those from late antiquity and the early medieval period, have long been a cornerstone of our understanding of historical developments, social structures, and cultural transformations (Merrills 2005). These chronicles, written primarily by male clerics, scholars, and chroniclers, have traditionally reflected the perspectives and biases of their authors. As a result, the narratives within these chronicles often emphasize the roles and actions of men, while the contributions of women are marginalized, misrepresented, or omitted altogether (Gos 2012).

The gender biases inherent in these historical sources have far-reaching implications. They shape our understanding of the past and influence contemporary perceptions of gender roles and relations. The marginalisation of women in historical narratives creates a skewed vision of history, where the contributions of half of the population are rendered invisible. This invisibility extends beyond individual women to the roles, occupations, and social dynamics in which women played significant parts (MacCarron 2022). Therefore, there is a critical need to re-evaluate these historical sources, bringing to light the stories, roles, and impacts of women that have been overlooked or suppressed.

Recent advancements in digital humanities offer new avenues for such re-evaluation, especially explored in the works of Pádraig MacCarron, and Kenna 2013 and Pádraig MacCarron 2014. The advent of digital tools and methods, such as network visualisation

¹M. MacCarron 2019

and digital text analysis, provides researchers with innovative ways to examine and interpret historical texts. These tools allow for the analysis of large bodies of text, uncovering patterns, connections, and themes that might not be immediately apparent through traditional methods of research. By applying these tools, researchers can re-assess these texts with a critical focus on gender representation, revealing the systemic biases that have shaped our understanding of the past. However, most of the visualisation tools lack features to represent gender and provide a dynamic environment for the researchers. We often see these tools cater to single datasets that allow analysis of project-specific objectives.

The motivation for this study stems from this dilemma. First, we seek to design a dynamic visualisation tool that can visualise any gendered networks within historical chronicles. Secondly, we aim to compare the existing tools and studies with our tool to highlight its features and design choices that make it unique. Finally, we want to address the limitations of these visualisation tools in analysing these historical chronicle data. This research endeavours to uncover new insights into the role of visualisation tools in exploring representations of women in late antiquity and the early medieval period, thereby contributing to a more inclusive and accurate understanding of history.

1.1 Research Questions

Building upon the research motivation and problems outlined in the previous section, this study is driven by the need to design and optimise visual analytics tools that effectively highlight and analyse gendered networks within historical chronicles, particularly those of the late antique and early medieval periods. The research questions guiding this study are formulated to address the core challenges of this task:

RQ1: How can visual analytics tools be designed to effectively highlight gendered networks within historical chronicles, particularly those from the late antique and early medieval periods?

This question is central to the study's objective of developing tools to reveal and visually represent gender dynamics within historical texts. It seeks to explore the design principles and methodologies that can be employed to ensure that these tools not only display networks but also bring the often-overlooked roles and connections of women to the forefront. The answer to this question will involve a detailed examination of the features, algorithms, and visual elements that most effectively highlight gendered relationships in complex historical datasets.

RQ2: In what ways do the design choices of visual analytics tools influence the interpretation of gendered data in historical chronicles, and how can these tools be optimized for accuracy and clarity?

This question addresses the critical issue of how design decisions impact the effectiveness and reliability of visual analytics tools in representing gendered networks. The study will investigate how different design elements, such as node

shapes, colours, and layouts, affect the way users perceive and interpret gender data. By comparing various existing visualisation tools, the research aims to identify the most effective design choices that enhance the clarity and precision of gender representation. This question also seeks to uncover potential biases or distortions introduced by certain design decisions and to propose optimisations that mitigate these issues.

RQ3: What are the challenges and limitations associated with using visual analytics tools to study gendered networks in historical chronicles, and how can these challenges be addressed to improve the representation of women?

Although visual analytics tools offer significant potential to uncover gendered networks, they also present unique challenges and limitations. This question aims to critically evaluate these challenges, which may include technical constraints, the complexity of accurately representing historical relationships, and the potential for modern biases to influence interpretations. The study will explore strategies to overcome these limitations, ensuring that the tools developed are robust, reliable, and capable of providing a nuanced understanding of women's roles in historical narratives. Addressing this question will contribute to the broader goal of optimizing digital humanities methodologies for gender studies, ensuring that the tools used in this research and future studies are well-equipped to handle the complexities of historical gender analysis.

Together, these research questions will guide the development of this thesis and the evaluation of our visual analytics tool. This will ensure the tool's functionality of gathering insightful results capable of challenging the traditional narratives that have marginalized women in history. Further, these questions will also help us understand the role of visual analytics in historical social network research and its potential limitations. By addressing these questions, the study aims to contribute to the growing field of digital humanities and to the ongoing efforts to create a more inclusive and accurate understanding of the past.

1.2 Significance of Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to make meaningful contributions to both historical scholarship and the field of digital humanities, particularly in the area of gender studies. We focus on the design and optimisation of visual analytics tools to highlight gendered networks within historical chronicles. Therefore, this research addresses a critical gap in the current methodologies used to study historical records M. MacCarron 2022 Hillner, M. MacCarron, and Vihervalli 2022. Traditional historical analyses often overlook or marginalise the contributions of women due to inherent biases in the sources and interpretive frameworks employed by historians Albayrak 2023. This study seeks to rectify this by developing tools specifically designed to uncover and visualise the often hidden roles of women in history. By employing innovative digital

tools, this study not only seeks to bring to light the contributions of women but also to challenge and redefine the existing historical narratives. The insights gained from this research have the potential to reshape our understanding of these periods by offering a more balanced and inclusive portrayal of the past.

Moreover, the study's focus on the design choices in visual analytics tools highlights the importance of methodological rigour in digital humanities. The research will explore how different design elements, such as node shapes, colours, and layouts, influence the interpretation of gendered data. By doing so, it will contribute to the broader field of data visualisation, offering guidelines and best practices for designing tools that are not only effective but also sensitive to the nuances of gender representation. This aspect of the study is crucial to ensure that digital tools do not inadvertently perpetuate the biases they aim to overcome.

Furthermore, by critically evaluating the challenges and limitations of using visual analytics tools to study gendered networks, this research will provide valuable insight into how these tools can be refined and improved. The study's findings will be relevant not only to historians and gender studies scholars but also to developers of digital humanities tools, offering them practical strategies for enhancing the accuracy and clarity of gender representation in historical research.

In summary, the significance of this study extends beyond the specific historical periods it examines. Advancing the methodologies used to study gender in historical records, contributes to the ongoing efforts to create a more inclusive and accurate understanding of history. Furthermore, by addressing the technical and interpretive challenges associated with digital tools, this research paves the way for future studies that can analyse and visualise the complex dynamics of gender more effectively in historical narratives.

1.3 Thesis Structure

The structure of this thesis is designed to systematically address the research questions and objectives, offering a logical progression from the theoretical foundation to the practical application of digital methods in historical analysis. The thesis is organised into six chapters, each serving a distinct purpose in the overall narrative of the research. This chapter discusses the biases in women's representation in historical chronicle data, our motivation to develop visualisation tools that ensure proper gender representation, and outlines the key research questions (RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3) driving this study, emphasizing the significance of addressing these issues. Chapter 2 delves into the theoretical background and literature, focusing on visual analytics, network analysis, and the role of gender in historical studies. Chapter 3 provides an overview of the historical chronicle datasets selected for this research, including the criteria for selection, data preparation, and preprocessing methods. In Chapter 4, we detail the methodology, covering the design and implementation of our visualisation tool and the specific techniques used to analyze gendered networks within these historical datasets. Chapter 5 presents the results of our analysis using our tool, offering insights into the roles of women in historical

networks and comparing these with existing historical interpretations. Lastly, Chapter 6 summarizes the main findings and contributions of this research, discusses the limitations faced, and proposes future research directions within the fields of Historical Social Network Analysis (HSNA) and digital humanities.

Chapter 2

Background

"The most compelling insight often comes from visualizing data in ways that reveal the patterns and relationships that matter."

— David McCandless, *Information is Beautiful* 2012 ¹

The study of history has long been shaped by chronological frameworks that are predominantly male-centric, often sidelining or entirely omitting the experiences and contributions of women Caviness 2001. This is particularly evident in late antiquity and the early Middle Ages, where primary chronological systems, such as those based on imperial, regnal, and consular years, are inherently linked to male figures. Despite the male-dominated nature of these systems, they are frequently perceived as neutral and objective, perpetuating a biased historical narrative. This study seeks to challenge these systemic biases by designing gendered visualisation frameworks to represent complex historical networks from these narratives.

This literature review chapter aims to lay the foundational groundwork for understanding the intersection of visual analytics, gender, chronology, and digital methods in historical research. In this chapter, we examine the existing body of work on visual analytics, gender and chronology, digital humanities, and the biases inherent in historical writing through the lenses of social networks. This chapter will provide a comprehensive overview of the current state of research and highlight the gaps that this research seeks to address.

The chapter is structured as follows: The first section explores the context of visualisation, particularly information visualisations and the role of visual analytics in addressing chronological frameworks. Secondly, we explore the historical context of gender in chronology, examining how traditional chronological frameworks have marginalized women's roles and contributions. The second section delves into the social network visualisations, delving deep inside to address the mathematical and theoretical foundations of social networks and insights gathered from them. Further, in this section, we also discuss the role of social network visualisations in studying historical chronological

¹McCandless 2012

networks and analysing the role of entities based on the grounds of factors like gender, background, social beliefs and so on.

Through this comprehensive review, the chapter aims to elucidate the significance of a gender-focused re-evaluation of time and chronology, underscoring the potential of digital methods to uncover and address the systemic biases that have long shaped historical narratives. This foundation will support the overarching aim of this study is to design network visualisation tools that incorporate proper gender representation using historical chronicle data.

2.1 Visualisation

Visualisation is frequently described as "the use of computer-assisted, interactive visual representations of data to enhance cognitive processes" Card, Mackinlay, and Shneiderman 1999. By presenting data graphically, we can use our visual system to improve knowledge acquisition, leading to more informed decision-making, clearer communication, and potential new insights Pister 2022. Visualisation plays a critical role in the field of historical research, particularly in the study of large complex data sets such as those found in medieval literature and historical chronologies. As the digital age brings an influx of data, the challenge lies not just in data collection, but in its interpretation. This section explores how visualisation, especially information visualisation and visual analytics, has become a vital tool in addressing these challenges, providing historians with new insights into historical data. The focus will be on understanding the principles, techniques, and applications of visualisation in historical research, with an emphasis on how these methods can be used to uncover gender roles in historical chronicles.

2.1.1 Information Visualisation in Historical Research

Information visualisation is described as leveraging computer-supported visual representations to manage large amounts of data effectively. The overarching goal is to turn information overload into an opportunity, enhancing the ability to process, analyze, and make decisions based on data Keim et al. 2008. Card, Mackinlay, and Shneiderman 1999 refers to the use of computer-supported interactive visual representations of abstract data to amplify cognition, such as information visualisation. In historical research, this involves the transformation of historical data into visual formats that allow historians to perceive patterns, trends, and anomalies that would otherwise remain hidden in traditional textual formats. The primary goal of information visualisation is to provide insight rather than merely presenting data Ware 2019.

The development of information visualisation has its roots in scientific visualisation, where it was originally used to handle large sets of scientific data McCormick 1988. However, as the complexity of data in the humanities grew, the need to extend these techniques into the realm of abstract data became evident Card, Mackinlay, and Shneiderman 1999. Visualisation allows for the representation of historical entities and their

relationships in ways that highlight significant features and facilitate deeper analysis Tufte 1991.

In historical research, information visualisation is particularly valuable in exploring temporal and spatial relationships. For example, mapping out the interactions between different historical figures over time can reveal patterns of influence and power that are not immediately apparent from the text alone. These visual representations help historians to reframe historical narratives, particularly in re-evaluating the roles of marginalized groups such as women (Tufte 1991; Card, Mackinlay, and Shneiderman 1999).

Information visualisation in history can be used to transform our understanding of past social dynamics by visualising relationships that are not immediately evident from traditional sources. This can include the examination of political alliances, familial relationships, or the spread of social movements as explored by Staley in his book in the early 2000s Staley 2015. Recent approaches in historical research have utilized various techniques to enhance the effectiveness of visualisation. For example, Y. Zhang et al. 2022 used Geographic Information Systems (GIS) to reconstruct historical maps, specifically focusing on the spatial data of the coastal military defence system of the Ming Dynasty. This method combines quantitative analysis with visual representation, allowing a more comprehensive display and analysis of historical information, which aids in understanding the spatial relationships and accessibility of military settlements. In addition, the integration of temporal and spatial data through visualisation tools has been emphasized by various studies. For example, Z. Wang 2017 discussed the role of visualizing historical spatial data to facilitate the study of economic history, highlighting how such techniques can reveal hidden economic patterns over time.

These approaches demonstrate the growing importance of information visualisation in historical research, where advanced visualisation methods not only enhance the interpretation of complex datasets but also contribute to the discovery of new historical narratives and insights.

2.1.2 Visual Analytics in Addressing Historical Sources

Visual analytics can be considered a growing transformative tool to gather insights from a wide range of data Cui 2019 Afzal et al. 2023. Visual analytics is defined as the science of analytical reasoning facilitated by interactive visual interfaces Keim et al. 2008. It combines the strengths of human intuition and perception with the processing power of computers to enable the exploration of large-scale complex datasets. The primary goal is to turn the information overload into an opportunity by making the data analysis process transparent, allowing better decision-making and deeper understanding of the data Y. Zhang et al. 2022. Visual analytics plays an important role in the study of historical chronicles Han et al. 2021 John et al. 2017 Cho et al. 2015, allowing the reevaluation of traditional narratives and the discovery of hidden patterns, including those related to gender roles and social structures Damann, Siow, and Tavits 2023 Cabric et al. 2023. This section discusses the application of visual analytics, particularly network visualisation

and spatial analysis, to the study of historical chronicles, integrating insights from a variety of recent academic works. By analyzing these papers and the methodologies they explore, this section underscores the advancements in the field while identifying challenges and opportunities for future research.

The concept of visual analytics, as outlined by Keim et al. 2008, integrates analytical reasoning with interactive visual interfaces, allowing for the effective exploration and study of large, complex data. This framework has been particularly influential in historical research, where visual analytics provides a way to analyze chronological data embedded in historical texts. The VAIroma project, described by Cho et al. 2015, is an exemplary application of this approach, combining text analysis with a visual interface to explore Roman history. VAIroma enables researchers to uncover connections that are not immediately apparent through traditional methods by linking places, events, and timelines. Another significant advancement in the field is the use of network visualisation and spatial analysis. In their analysis of the *Íslendinga Sögur*, Pádraig MacCarron, and Kenna 2013 used network analysis to explore the social structures within Icelandic sagas. Their work showed that saga societies exhibited complex social networks similar to real-world societies, highlighting the applicability of network theory to historical chronicles and the potential of visual analytics to offer quantitative insights into historical narratives. More recently, Yose et al. 2018 utilized network analysis to study the Viking Age in Ireland, as depicted in the *Cogadh Gaedhel re Gallaibh*. This work highlighted how network science could reveal intricate social and political relationships within historical texts, challenging the traditional, often oversimplified, narrative of Viking interactions with the Irish. The use of network visualisation is a remarkable step in understanding relationship dynamics and influences in any social environment. In the next section, we will explore the use of complex social networks in detail. Further advancements are evident in the work of Besnier 2020, who employed social network analysis to compare the evolution of character importance in the *Siegfried-Sigurd* myth across different historical sources. By constructing character networks from texts like *The Nibelungenlied* and *Volsunga saga*, Besnier was able to quantify the shifts in character prominence over time, providing insights into how historical events may have been reinterpreted in later mythological narratives. Additionally, He et al. 2022 explores the integration of cultural and historical data especially gender and social roles like occupation and status into visualisations that are used to represent the unique cultural characteristics of Dengfeng City. This study primarily contributes to the broader field of visual analytics by demonstrating how complex cultural information from local chronicles can be extensively visualized to enhance public understanding and engagement with historical and cultural content.

Han et al. 2021 in their HisVA project combines geospatial analysis and relationship mapping to connect historical events geographically. HisVA allows researchers to visualize relationships between historical figures, events, and their geographical contexts, offering a multi-dimensional perspective on historical narratives. This tool is particularly valuable in exploring how social and spatial factors interact over time, which is essential for understanding the dynamics of historical chronicles. Similarly,

ScrollTimes, as described by W. Zhang et al. 2024, leverages visual analytics to trace the provenance of paintings, providing art historians with a tool to explore the cultural and historical context embedded in traditional Chinese handscrolls. The system constructs "biographies" of handscrolls by integrating multiple data sources, allowing for a detailed exploration of the artefact's history and its interaction with different cultural figures and events over time. This approach is analogous to the study of historical chronicles, where understanding the provenance and context of historical records can lead to new insights into the past.

2.1.3 Integration of Gender Analysis into Visual Analytics

The integration of gender analysis into visual analytics is a growing trend in historical research, reflecting the need for more inclusive approaches in visual data representation. The study by Cabric et al. 2023 on gender data visualisation underscores the challenges in accurately representing gender data and avoiding stereotypes in visualisations. Mapping social networks and exploring the roles of women within these networks can help uncover the often-overlooked contributions of women in historical narratives.

In the book "*Maths meets myths*" Kenna, Maccarron, and Padraig MacCarron 2017 The chapter by Yuriy Holovatch and Vasyl Palchykov Holovatch, and Palchykov 2017 delves into the application of complex network theory to the analysis of fables. By mapping out the relationships between words and their frequency of occurrence, this approach provides a novel way of understanding the narrative structures of fables. This methodology can be extended to historical chronicles, allowing researchers to uncover the underlying patterns and structures in these texts. Such patterns can reveal biases in how historical events and figures, including women, are represented within these chronicles, contributing to the broader field of visual analytics in historical research. The chapter by Gramsch et al. 2017 is particularly valuable for integrating gender analysis into visual analytics. The authors examine how gender influences the construction of social networks in medieval texts, focusing on the roles of women in these networks. By applying network analysis, the chapter reveals how certain texts elevate or diminish the roles of women, providing a quantitative approach to understanding gender dynamics in historical narratives. This work underscores the importance of considering gender as a critical dimension in visual analytics, enabling historians to uncover biases in how women are portrayed in historical records. Further, Isolde Thyrêt in her work Thyrêt 2018 explores the portrayal of Muscovite royal women, particularly focusing on the visual and literary depiction of Grand Princess Evdokiia. This work significantly contributes to the integration of gender analysis into visual analytics by highlighting how visual representations and literary texts collaboratively construct and reinforce the roles of royal women in historical narratives. Thyrêt's analysis underscores the importance of understanding the intersection between visual imagery and gender, demonstrating how visual analytics can reveal the complexities and symbolic importance of female figures in shaping political and religious narratives in Muscovite Russia.

M. MacCarron 2022 explored how network visualisation could be used to uncover

the roles of women in medieval religious communities, which are often marginalized in traditional historical narratives. This research demonstrates how visual analytics can be used to identify and correct biases in historical records, offering a more inclusive view of history. By visualizing the interactions and contributions of women, MacCarron's work highlights the potential of visual analytics to challenge and reframe historical narratives. Similarly, in their chapter "A Network Approach: Tracking Female Power in Seven Epic Narratives," Pádraig MacCarron, M. MacCarron, et al. 2024 provides an excellent example of how network analysis can be used to compare the influence of female characters across different cultures and periods. Their study analyzed seven epic narratives, including ancient texts like the *Iliad* and *Beowulf*, as well as modern works like *The Lord of the Rings*. The network analysis revealed that while male characters generally held the most influence, female characters in the *Laxdæla Saga* had relatively more influence compared to other works. This finding aligns with traditional narrative analyses but also demonstrates the power of visual analytics to offer new insights into gender dynamics across different historical contexts.

2.1.4 Challenges and Tribulations

Despite the significant advancements in visual analytics, several challenges remain. The quality and completeness of the historical data are primary concerns, as highlighted by Keim et al. 2008. Historical records are often fragmented or biased, limiting the insights that can be gained from visual analytics tools. For example, M. MacCarron 2022 noted the scarcity of first-hand accounts from female religious communities in medieval times, making it challenging to fully reconstruct these narratives using visual analytics.

Another challenge is the interpretation of visualisations. While visual analytics can reveal complex patterns and relationships, interpreting these visualisations accurately requires a high level of expertise. There is a risk of oversimplification or misinterpretation, particularly when dealing with complex historical data. The need for interdisciplinary collaboration between historians, computer scientists, and graphic designers is crucial to developing tools that are both user-friendly and methodologically rigorous Han et al. 2021 W. Zhang et al. 2024.

The study by Besnier 2020 also highlights the importance of careful data preparation and the potential pitfalls of relying solely on automated methods for character extraction and interaction analysis. The study's findings underscore the need for combining automated techniques with domain expertise to ensure that the resulting visualisations are accurate and meaningful.

2.2 Complex Social Networks

In the previous section, we explored how social networks have been frequently used as visual analytics tools to study relationship dynamics, gender roles, and social environments in historical chronicle networks. Complex social networks have been particularly useful for understanding the relational concepts of kinship, sociopolitical influences,

geospatial relationships, and the characterization of communities in past societies. Researchers have effectively used these networks to model and analyze the intricate connections that define social structures extracted from chronicle and historical data. These social connections can further be analysed by leveraging network measures and visualisation techniques to reveal structural and social observations. The application of complex social networks in the context of historical chronicle research has also allowed for the integration of analysing various roles in their social representation, especially gender analysis. Thus, providing insights into the roles and influences of women in historical contexts. As social networks are mapped and analyzed, the relative positions and connections of women within these networks can be assessed, offering a more nuanced understanding of their roles in historical narratives. In this section, we will provide a detailed overview of complex social networks by delving deep into the concepts of SNA. We will start by discussing the advent of SNA from sociometry, and then start by exploring how complex networks are formed and represented. Further, we will discuss the concepts related to SNA visualisations, measures, layouts and tools.

2.2.1 Sociometry and Complex Social Networks

The evolution of Social Network Analysis (SNA) from its origins in sociometry reflects a significant transformation in the study of social relationships and structures. Sociometry, introduced by Jacob Moreno in the 1930s, was among the first systematic attempts to map and quantify interpersonal relationships within small groups. Moreno's approach was innovative in its use of sociograms, which visually represented individuals as nodes and their relationships as edges. This method provided a powerful tool for understanding the social dynamics within groups, emphasizing the importance of direct observation of social bonds rather than relying on abstract social categories such as class or status Moreno 1943.

Moreno's work in 1943 was a response to the limitations of traditional sociological methods, which often relied on predefined taxonomies to categorize individuals based on factors such as age, gender, and social status. These traditional approaches were criticized for their potential biases and for removing individuals from their social contexts. For instance, Allen Barton famously critiqued the use of random sampling in surveys, arguing that such methods could strip away the social context that is crucial for understanding individual behaviour. He described traditional surveys as a "sociological meatgrinder," which isolated individuals from their natural social environments, thereby limiting the insights that could be gained from such studies Barton 1968. However, Moreno's work in sociometrics would lay the foundations of SNA which will be explored in the subsequent discussion. Moreno pioneered a new method for understanding the social structures within groups and organizations by visualizing actual social interactions. He introduced sociograms, where circles represented individuals and lines depicted the friendships between them. One of his early sociograms represented in Figure 2.1 illustrates the friendships among eighth-grade students. The sociological and mathematical implications of Moreno's work have been extensively

Figure 2.1: Moreno’s original sociogram of a class of 8th grades from (left). The diagram shows 21 boys (triangles) and 14 girls (circles) Moreno 1934. The same sociogram using modern practices generated using Python with (right). The node sizes the number of incoming connections.

discussed in thousands of publications. However, beyond the theoretical contributions, it is important to consider the visual practices introduced by Moreno. His hand-drawn sociograms, while groundbreaking, introduced certain visual biases, particularly due to his decision to separate girls and boys into two predefined groups. This separation sometimes overlooked the more complex community structures that existed within these groups, such as the inter-sexual “bridges” that formed between boys and girls, which were not the only structural connections within the network. Modern visualisations of such networks as shown in the same Figure 2.1 (right) addresses these biases by employing techniques like adjusting the size and colour of nodes to enhance the clarity and interpretability of the graph’s structure done using modern tools like Python. Additionally, Moreno’s early metrics, such as identifying “unchosen” individuals, “stars,” and “triangles,” prefigure some of the centrality measures used in contemporary network analysis to describe the roles and importance of different nodes within a network. These visual and analytical innovations have significantly influenced the development of SNA as a robust field of study Grandjean 2015.

Sociometry sought to address these limitations by focusing on real social interactions and the direct observation of relationships within groups. However, while sociometry provided a useful tool for visualizing social relationships, it lacked the formal mathematical foundation needed to analyze larger and more complex networks systematically. The mathematical rigour necessary for such analysis came from the field of graph theory, which was developed around the same time as sociometry. Graph theory provided a formal framework for representing social networks as graphs, where

nodes represent individuals and edges represent relationships. The first formal work in graph theory was published by Dénes König in 1936, laying the groundwork for the integration of graph theory into the study of social networks König 1990. By the 1950s, mathematicians like Frank Harary and sociologists such as Dorwin Cartwright began applying graph theory to sociological problems, developing more formalized methods for analyzing social networks. Harary's work Harary, and Norman 1953 was instrumental in bridging the gap between sociometry and what we now recognize as Social Network Analysis. He demonstrated how the mathematical properties of graphs² could be used to study social structures, enabling researchers to quantify aspects of social networks such as centrality, connectivity, and density. In the following years, many social researchers and mathematicians extended Harary's work on computational networks Mitchell 1969 Freeman 2004 while a group of researchers like Paul Erdős started to work on random graph models Erdos, Rényi, et al. 1960.

A graph³ is an abstract data structure which consists of nodes as entities and edges representing connections or relationships. This simple idea lays the foundation of complex analysis and observations. Mathematically, a graph is noted as:

$$G = (V, E) \tag{2.1}$$

with V a set of vertices representing entities like people, groups, and organisations and $E \subseteq V^2$ a set of edges modelling social relationships between the entities. The transition from sociometry to SNA marked a significant shift in the study of social relationships, from a focus on small groups to the analysis of large-scale social systems. This shift was made possible by the formal mathematical tools provided by graph theory, which allowed researchers to model and analyze social networks with greater precision and rigour. The development of network measures, such as centrality and clustering coefficients, enabled sociologists to explore the underlying structures of social networks and to understand how these structures influenced social behaviour.

2.2.2 Methods and Measures in Social Network Analysis

The advent of sociometric SNA has paved the way to understand the complexities of social structures. Through the application of graph theory, SNA allows researchers to uncover patterns, identify influential actors, and understand the intricacies of relationships within a network. This section delves into the fundamental methods and measures used in SNA, such as centrality measures, clustering, shortest paths, subgraphs, graphlets, and community detection, all of which are supported by robust mathematical foundations and visualisations. To explore these concepts further using visual analytics, we will discuss how these concepts have been applied in the study of literary networks, taking

²Graphs and networks refer to the same thing but are often used in different contexts. The term graph is preferred in a mathematical and abstract setting, while the term network is mostly used when modelling real-world phenomena.

³In this thesis, sometimes "graph" and "network" and "node" and "vertex" have been used interchangeably.

J.R.R. Tolkien's work *The Lord of the Rings* as a case study. We pick this example as a precursor to further exploring chronicle data in historical text. We have seen Pádraig MacCarron, M. MacCarron, et al. 2024 use a similar approach to explain key concepts in SNA visualisations using popular fictional literary works.

Centrality Measures

Centrality measures are essential in SNA as they help identify the most significant or influential nodes within a network. Each centrality measure offers a unique lens through which the importance of nodes can be assessed. They provide a structural overview of the network, highlighting the importance of nodes. The "importance" of nodes can be perceived in many ways like several connections it has, and the relative position of the node from an influential node Borgatti 2005. It can also represent the cohesiveness of the node with other nodes Borgatti, and Everett 2006. In addition, it is often the case that conclusions drawn from centrality scores evaluated under different perceptions yield different results Borgatti 2005. Therefore, centralities can be assessed from singular path length to infinite path lengths Bonacich 1987 Benzi, and Klymko 2014. Based on different categories of perception we shall further discuss each type's centralities in detail.

Degree Centrality: Degree centrality is the simplest and most intuitive measure of centrality. It is defined as the number of direct connections that a node has. In mathematical terms, for a node v in a graph $G = (V, E)$, the degree centrality $C_D(v)$ is expressed as:

$$C_D(v) = \deg(v) = |\{e = (v, u) \in E\}| \quad (2.2)$$

Nodes with a higher degree of centrality are considered more central or influential within the network. Figure 2.2 uses a small pool of characters from *Lord of the Rings* text to visualize a network where the sizes of the nodes are relative to their corresponding centralities. The figure (top right) shows the degree of centrality of these characters. In the context of this network high degree centrality nodes such as Aragorn and Frodo in Tolkien's works, are often central to the narrative and have numerous interactions with other characters. This concept has been effectively applied in studies Ribeiro et al. 2016 John et al. 2017 where the centrality of characters was assessed based on their degree of connection.

Betweenness Centrality Betweenness centrality goes beyond immediate connections and measures the extent to which a node acts as a bridge within the network. Specifically, it calculates how often a node lies on the shortest path between other nodes. The betweenness centrality $C_B(v)$ for a node v is defined as:

$$C_B(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t \in V} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 2.2: Degree centrality (top left), Betweenness centrality (top middle), closeness centrality (top right), eigenvector centrality (bottom left), Louvain community (bottom middle) and shortest path from Frodo to Galadriel nodes (bottom left), crafted from a smaller sample of *Lord of the Rings* characters.

where σ_{st} represents the total number of shortest paths from node s to node t , and $\sigma_{st}(v)$ is the number of those paths that pass through v . Nodes with high betweenness centrality, such as Aragorn and Frodo, play crucial roles in facilitating interactions between different parts of the network as shown in Figure 2.2 (top middle). This measure is particularly useful in understanding key characters who serve as connectors between various subgroups within a narrative, as explored in Pádraig MacCarron, M. MacCarron, et al. 2024. This concept of characters who act as a bridge between other characters or groups also serves as a tool for story progression and engagement as explored by Busselle, and Bilandzic 2009. Similarly, Masías et al. 2017 explored this property of betweenness centrality to study the prominence of characters in Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*.

Closeness Centrality Closeness centrality measures the efficiency with which a node can access all other nodes in the network. It is calculated as the inverse of the sum of the shortest path distances from a given node to all other nodes in the network:

$$C_C(v) = \frac{1}{\sum_{t \in V} d(v, t)} \quad (2.4)$$

Nodes with high closeness centrality are positioned to quickly disseminate information throughout the network. In figure 2.2 (top right), characters like Aragorn and Frodo, who are central to the narrative and have relatively short paths to other characters, are typically more influential in the spread of information or influence within the story. This measure can be directly derived from betweenness centrality. The representation of centrality in equation 2.4 is the un-normalized version of closeness and is also known as status Harary 1959 Wuchty, and Stadler 2003. Gramsch-Stehfest 2020 explores that closeness centrality in historical medieval networks captures geographical, political as well as social closeness to other actors⁴ in the network. Therefore, this measure allows researchers to explore the power dynamics, and flow of information (Salavati, Abdollahpouri, and Manbari 2019) within historical social networks.

Eigenvector Centrality Eigenvector centrality extends the concept of degree centrality by considering not only the quantity of connections but also the quality of those connections. A node connected to other well-connected nodes will have a higher eigenvector centrality Newman 2008. Mathematically, it is defined as the eigenvector corresponding to the largest eigenvalue of the adjacency matrix A of the graph:

$$A\mathbf{x} = \lambda\mathbf{x} \quad (2.5)$$

In Figure 2.2 (bottom left), characters like Aragorn, and Frodo Gandalf, who are well-connected and linked to other central characters, exhibit high eigenvector centrality. This measure is particularly valuable for identifying characters who, although not

⁴In Complex Social Networks nodes often represent people and are called actors. Jamali, and Abolhassani 2006

necessarily having the most connections, are connected to other influential characters, thus amplifying their importance in the network Trusov, Bodapati, and Bucklin 2010. Zaki, and Meira 2014 has also used the term prestige score to refer to the eigenvector centrality, as it essentially identifies the most prestigious nodes in a network. This centrality is widely used in academic social networks to represent influential authors in a network Gayen et al. 2024. In the context of historical chronicles, it is paramount to trace the influential people in the chronicles, as well as to study their roles Merelo, and Molinari 2024. Pádraig MacCarron, M. MacCarron, et al. 2024 and Yose et al. 2018 also explore this concept while studying the role of women in the Viking age in Ireland.

Clustering and Cohesion

Clustering in networks refers to the tendency of nodes to form tightly-knit groups, which is indicative of strong community structures. The *clustering coefficient* is a key measure used to quantify this tendency, defined as the ratio of the number of closed triplets (triangles) to the number of possible triplets in the network:

$$C(v) = \frac{2e(v)}{k(v)(k(v) - 1)} \quad (2.6)$$

where $e(v)$ represents the number of edges between the neighbors of v , and $k(v)$ is the degree of v . A high clustering coefficient indicates that the network has strong community structures, which can be seen in subgraph visualisations where characters form tightly-knit groups. These groups often represent social circles, alliances, closed or open groups, or communities within the narrative. Figure 2.2 (bottom middle) shows community structures, in which you can see the fellowship comprising of Gandalf, Frodo and the hobbits, Aragon, Gimli, Boromir and Legolas forms a strong cohesive group. Within the fellowship, you can see the hobbits except for Frodo from a much closer group, while the elves have their community Tolkien 2022. Y. Li, Shang, and Yang 2017 explores the application of the clustering coefficient in studying how closed groups are formed in medieval Italian families. Watts, and Strogatz 1998 used the concept of clustering coefficient as a criterion for the formulation of small-world networks which is discussed further in the next section.

Network cohesion refers to the overall connectedness of a network, which can be measured using network density. Network density is defined as:

$$\text{Density} = \frac{2|E|}{|V|(|V| - 1)} \quad (2.7)$$

A dense network, where most possible connections are realised, indicates a high level of interconnectedness and strong social cohesion. Entwisle et al. 2007 and Bott, and Spillius 2014 explore how network cohesion is used to analyse family ties or kinship in anthropological social networks. In addition, Warner, Bowers, and Dixon 2012 explores how network cohesion is used to analyse team dynamics in sports.

Shortest Path

The concept of a shortest path is central to understanding the efficiency of a network. The shortest path between two nodes is the minimum number of edges that must be traversed to travel from one node to another. In unweighted graphs, the shortest path can be found using algorithms like Breadth-First Search (BFS) Goldberg, and Harrelson 2005, while in weighted graphs, Dijkstra's algorithm Dijkstra 2022 is typically used:

$$d(v, t) = \min \sum w(e) \quad (2.8)$$

where $w(e)$ represents the weight of edge e . The visualisation in Figure 2.2 (bottom right) shows the shortest path between Frodo and Galadriel, highlighted in the network, demonstrating the most efficient route through the network. This concept is crucial for understanding the narrative flow in literary networks, where the shortest path can indicate the most direct connections between key characters. Fazioli 2008 explores how the shortest path is important to identify the most critical trade routes that connect different regions, thus facilitating economic and cultural exchanges during the medieval era. In addition, Gramsch et al. 2017 and later Sarkanych et al. 2022 used the shortest path to identify how efficiently information or influence could flow between characters within the narrative of medieval literature and East-Slavic epics, respectively. By examining these paths, the authors discovered central characters who act as pivotal points in the narrative, effectively bridging different parts of the network.

Subgraphs and Graphlets

Subgraphs and graphlets provide a focused view of smaller sections within a larger network, offering insights into the local topology and revealing recurring patterns or motifs Dunne, and Shneiderman 2013.

Subgraphs are smaller network sections, consisting of a subset of nodes and edges. Analyzing subgraphs allows researchers to zoom in on specific parts of a network, such as character interactions within a particular narrative arc or a subplot within a story. Fortunato 2010 explored how these subgraphs can be used to study modular structures in graphs which share a similarity, he called them communities.

Graphlets are specific types of subgraphs representing small, connected, non-isomorphic substructures. Graphlet analysis is used to characterize the local topology of networks by identifying common structural patterns Sarajlić et al. 2016. The subgraph visualisations presented in this study shown in Figure 2.7 illustrate various interactions among characters in Tolkien's works, highlighting the narrative's structural complexity. These patterns are essential for understanding the micro-structures that contribute to the overall narrative flow. Further, graphlet analysis can reveal the persistence or transformation of certain social patterns, offering a deeper understanding of historical continuity and change Yose et al. 2018 H. Li 2018.

Subgraphs and Graphlets in Grid Layout

Figure 2.3: All possible subgraphs and graphlets of triads and Quadruplets crafted from a smaller network sample of *Lord of the Rings* characters shown in Figure 2.2.

Community Detection

Community detection is a method used to identify groups of nodes that are more densely connected than the rest of the network. Communities often represent real-world groupings such as social circles, factions, or clans within a story. The *Louvain method* first introduced by Blondel et al. 2008a is a popular community detection algorithm that optimizes modularity, a measure of the strength of the division of a network into communities.

$$Q = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{ij} \left[A_{ij} - \frac{k_i k_j}{2m} \right] \delta(c_i, c_j) \quad (2.9)$$

where A_{ij} is the adjacency matrix, k_i and k_j are the degrees of nodes i and j , and $\delta(c_i, c_j)$ is 1 if nodes i and j are in the same community. The Louvain method has been applied in the analysis of *Lord of the Rings* character network in Figure 2.2 (bottom right) reveals the distinct social groups or alliances that form within the story, such as the division between Elves, Dwarves, and Men.

Another community detection method, the *Girvan-Newman Algorithm*, detects communities by iteratively removing edges with the highest betweenness centrality. This process causes the network to break down into smaller components, each representing a community Girvan, and Newman 2002. This method is particularly effective in networks where communities are defined by bottlenecks or bridges between densely connected subgroups. As networks grow in size and complexity, visual clutter becomes a significant challenge, making it difficult to discern meaningful patterns. Techniques such as *edge bundling* and *motif simplification* are essential for managing this clutter and improving the clarity of visualisations Dunne, and Shneiderman 2013.

Edge bundling groups similar edges together, reducing visual noise and making the overall structure of the network more apparent. This technique is especially useful in dense networks where individual edges may overlap significantly, obscuring important patterns. Nguyen, Eades, and Hong 2013 explores the use of edge bundling to highlight major routes of communication or influence, such as trade networks or paths of migration. In historical chronicle networks, not all relationships carry the same weight. Edge bundling can emphasize more significant connections (e.g., repeated alliances or conflicts), helping to focus attention on the most important aspects of the network Wu et al. 2018.

Motif simplification, as discussed by Dunne, and Shneiderman 2013, involves replacing complex, repetitive motifs with simpler graphical representations or glyphs. This approach enhances the interpretability of network visualisations by making it easier to identify key structures and relationships within large datasets.

Furthermore, *graph drawing algorithms*, such as force-directed layouts and hierarchical layouts, play a crucial role in producing clear and informative network visualisations. Force-directed layouts position nodes based on simulated physical forces, which help reveal the natural structure of the network by minimising edge crossings and maintaining a balanced node distribution Fruchterman, and Reingold 1991. Hierarchi-

cal layouts, on the other hand, are used to represent networks with a clear hierarchical structure, such as organisational charts or genealogical trees, where the relationships between nodes follow a strict order Sugiyama, Tagawa, and Toda 1981. We will discuss graph drawing algorithms and layouts extensively in the subsequent section.

2.2.3 Network Modelling

Network modelling is an essential process in SNA and Historical Chronicle Networks. It involves the abstraction and representation of social phenomena as mathematical structures—typically in the form of simple to complex graph structures. This modelling process enables researchers to apply computational methods to analyse social structures, offering deep insights into the dynamics of past societies. This section provides a detailed literature review of key concepts, methods, and tools used in network modelling, with a focus on applications in historical chronicle research.

Graph Theory and Network Structures

At the core of network modelling lies graph theory, the mathematical framework that forms the foundation for representing social networks. A graph $G = (V, E)$ consists of a set of vertices V (also called nodes) and a set of edges E (or links) that connect pairs of nodes. These structures can represent various entities and relationships in historical research, such as individuals, groups, institutions, and their interactions.

Undirected Graphs: Undirected graphs are used when relationships are bidirectional, such as mutual friendships or collaborations. In these graphs, the edges have no direction, meaning $(v_i, v_j) = (v_j, v_i)$. Mathematically, undirected graphs are represented as:

$$G = (V, E), \quad E \subseteq \{\{v_i, v_j\} : v_i, v_j \in V\} \quad (2.10)$$

These graphs are particularly useful in modelling symmetric relationships, such as mutual trade partnerships or alliances between medieval kingdoms. This type of graph is primarily used for showing the mutual relationships between various actors in a network. Yose et al. 2018 uses undirected graphs in their study of *Cogadh Gaedhel re Gallaibh* as shown in Figure 2.4

Directed Graphs: Directed graphs, or digraphs, are used when relationships have directionality, such as influence, command structures, or communication flows. Here, each edge is an ordered pair (v_i, v_j) , indicating that v_i influences v_j . A directed graph is represented as:

$$G = (V, E), \quad E \subseteq \{(v_i, v_j) : v_i, v_j \in V\} \quad (2.11)$$

Directed graphs are crucial in historical analyses where the flow of information or power is unidirectional, such as in feudal systems or military hierarchies. Brughmans

Figure 2.4: *Cogadh* networks where Viking nodes are represented as blue, Irish nodes as green and other nodes as grey. All edges connecting Irish nodes are coloured green, while Viking edges are coloured blue, while edges connecting Viking to Irish nodes are coloured brown. This is a good example of undirected networks showing mutual relationships Yose et al. 2018.

2013 employed directed graphs to study the connectivity and communication between different settlements in the Roman Empire. The work highlights the importance of directionality in understanding the flow of goods, information, and people across the empire. Similarly, LIU, WANG, and CHEN 2018 used directed graphs to analyze factional conflicts within the ruling class of the Northern Song Dynasty. This allowed the authors to study the power dynamics and flow of political influence within the dynasty. More recently, Emerson 2023 explored the transmission and ownership of manuscripts, where nodes represent individuals or institutions, and directed edges represent the flow of manuscripts between them. This approach helps identify key figures in the network who played a significant role in the dissemination of texts, highlighting the social and material bonds that facilitated the circulation of historical chronicles.

Bipartite Graphs: Bipartite graphs consist of two distinct sets of nodes, such as individuals and events, with edges that only connect nodes from different sets. These graphs are particularly effective in representing interactions between two types of entities in historical research. A bipartite graph $G = (V_1 \cup V_2, E)$ is defined as:

$$V_1 \cap V_2 = \emptyset, \quad E \subseteq \{(v_i, v_j) : v_i \in V_1, v_j \in V_2\} \quad (2.12)$$

In the context of historical networks, bipartite graphs are used to model interactions between social groups and events, such as parliamentary sessions and the participating members during the medieval period. In the context of mythological studies, bipartite graphs can effectively capture the complex relationships between characters and the events or actions in which they are involved Pádraig MacCarron 2014. In addition, Goddeeris 2022 employed bipartite graphs to analyse historical networks, specifically within the context of the Central Redistributive Household of Nippur in the 18th century BCE Sumeria. The study used bipartite graphs to effectively demonstrate how different individuals, especially women, were involved in the economic activities of the household, highlighting their role and influence within the ancient administrative system. Similarly, Błoch, Vasques Filho, and Bojanowski 2022 used bipartite graphs to represent official correspondence networks where one set of nodes represents correspondents (such as officials and merchants) and the other set represents locations or topics associated with the correspondence. This structure allowed the authors to analyse communication patterns and network dynamics within the Portuguese Empire.

Layered Graphs: Layered graphs are a specialised type of graph in which each node is assigned to a specific layer. These layers often correspond to hierarchical or temporal data, making them particularly useful in historical chronicle networks for representing events over time or hierarchical structures. The layout of layered graphs is optimised to minimise cross-sections and reduce visual clutter. The Stratisfimal Layout, an advanced algorithm discussed in Di Bartolomeo et al. 2021, provides a modular and optimal approach to arranging nodes in layered graphs by formulating the problem as an integer-linear programming task.

Graph Models: Random, Small-World, and Scale-Free Networks

Different graph models provide varying insights into the properties and dynamics of social networks. These models help researchers understand the structure, resilience, and evolution of networks, as well as the processes that generate them.

Random Graphs: In the late 1950s, Paul Erdős began studying the randomness of relationships. In his joint work with Alfréd Rényi in 1959 Erdos, Rényi, et al. 1960 he presented the Erds-Rényi network model, in which connections between nodes form randomly. In the ER model $G(n, p)$, each possible edge between n nodes is included with probability p . The degree distribution in a random graph follows a binomial distribution which, for large n , approximates a Poisson distribution:

$$P(k) = \binom{n-1}{k} p^k (1-p)^{n-1-k} \quad (2.13)$$

Figure 2.5: (a) Randomly generated Erdős-Rényi (ER) Network (b) Degree distribution of the graph with a probability of edge creation 0.02 for 1000 nodes

Random graphs are particularly useful for studying networks with a high degree of randomness, such as the spread of diseases in historical populations, where interactions occur by chance rather than through structured social processes Newman 2002. They are essentially used to analyse and compare social interaction patterns, particularly those without strong structural links Barabasi 2003.

Small-World Networks From the mid-1960s sociologists like Milgram and Korte studied the small world problem, which stated that in a social network, every person is mutually connected through a small number of intermediaries Kleinfeld 2002. In 1998 using this concept as a foundation, Watts and Strogatz (1998) Watts, and Strogatz 1998 introduced small-world networks. These small-world networks are characterised by a high degree of clustering and short average path lengths, reflecting patterns observed in

many real-world networks. The small-world model is constructed by randomly rewiring a regular lattice, producing a network where most nodes are not direct neighbours but can be reached from any other node through a small number of steps. The clustering coefficient C and the average path length L are key properties of small-world WS networks:

$$C = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{2 \times \text{edges between neighbors of } v_i}{k_i(k_i - 1)} \quad (2.14)$$

$$L = \frac{1}{n(n-1)} \sum_{i \neq j} \text{shortest path length}(v_i, v_j) \quad (2.15)$$

Figure 2.6: a) Small world network visualisation b) Degree distribution over 10 WS networks with 1000 vertices, $k = 25$ and $p = 0.3$

Small-world networks are prevalent in historical research for modelling tightly-knit social structures, such as intellectual networks in medieval Europe, where knowledge spread rapidly due to the small number of intermediary connections. Noble 2010 explored how small-world networks formed while modelling political alliances and feudal relationships in medieval Europe. These networks show how noble families were closely connected to their vassals within their regions, while also maintaining ties to other distant political entities. Malkin 2011 explored trade routes of ancient civilizations where the trade networks always had few central trade hubs that connected otherwise distant and isolated regions. This allowed efficient trade routes that contributed to economic and cultural exchange between ancient civilisations such as Egypt, Greece, and Rome. Furthermore recently, Mac Carron, and Kenna 2013 used small-world network analysis to the Icelandic sagas, revealing that the social networks within these ancient narratives exhibit short path lengths and high clustering coefficients, similar to real-life social networks. This suggests that the sagas may reflect realistic aspects of Viking society, offering a quantitative perspective on their historical authenticity.

Scale-Free Networks Scale-free networks are characterized by a power-law degree distribution, where a few nodes (hubs) have a very high degree while most nodes have a low degree. The Barabási–Albert (BA) model is a well-known method for generating scale-free networks. In the BA model, nodes are added to the network one at a time, with each new node preferentially attaching to existing nodes with higher degrees Barabási, and Albert 1999. The degree distribution follows:

$$P(k) \sim k^{-\gamma} \quad (2.16)$$

Figure 2.7: a) BA scale-free Network b) Degree distribution BA networks formed by 1000 vertices using $m = 5$

where γ is typically between 2 and 3. Scale-free networks are common in social systems where a few individuals or entities dominate, such as influential families in medieval societies or dominant trading hubs in historical economic networks. Pádraig MacCarron 2014 in their analysis of the chronicle network of Icelandic sagas confirms that the degree distribution of the network closely follows a power-law distribution, characteristic of scale-free networks. This finding suggests that the saga networks are scale-free, meaning that a few characters (hubs) are highly connected, while most characters have relatively few connections. Similarly, Yose et al. 2018 explored the social networks represented in the Viking Age chronicles by employing scale-free models. The authors demonstrate that the network of interactions among Viking leaders and events follows a scale-free distribution, where a few key leaders are central to most interactions, while the majority of characters have fewer connections. This is consistent with the fact that Viking leadership was hierarchical as the narrative is centered around these influential figures.

Role of Visual Analytics in Network Modelling

Visual analytics plays a crucial role in network modelling by providing tools for the visualisation, exploration, and interpretation of complex networks. Tools such as Com-

Table 2.1: Analytical result of some basic measurements for the Erdős-Rényi (ER), Watts-Strogatz (Ws), and Barabási-Albert (BA) network models L. da F. Costa, and Boas 2007.

Measurement	Erdős-Rényi	Watts-Strogatz	Barabási-Albert
Degree distribution	$P(k) = \frac{e^{-\langle k \rangle} \langle k \rangle^k}{k!}$	$P(k) = \sum_{i=1}^{\min(k-\kappa, \kappa)} \binom{\kappa}{i} (1-p)^i p^{\kappa-i} \frac{(p\kappa)^{k-\kappa-i}}{(k-\kappa-i)!} e^{-p\kappa}$	$P(k) \sim k^{-3}$
Average vertex degree	$\langle k \rangle = p(N-1)$	$\langle k \rangle = 2\kappa^5$	$\langle k \rangle = 2m$
Clustering coefficient	$C = p$	$C(p) \sim \frac{3(\kappa-1)}{2(2\kappa-1)} (1-p)^3$	$C \sim N^{-0.75}$
Average path length	$\ell \sim \frac{\ln N}{\ln \langle k \rangle}$	$\ell(N, p) \sim p^\tau f(Np^\tau)^6$	$\ell \sim \frac{\log N}{\log(\log N)}$

BiNet and PK-Clustering enhance the usability and effectiveness of network modelling in historical research. These tools allow historians to interactively explore network structures, detect patterns, and refine their models based on visual feedback.

ComBiNet: ComBiNet is designed for combining and analyzing complex networks with multiple layers or types of relationships Pister, Prieur, and Fekete 2023. Supports dynamic and multivariate network analysis, allowing users to visualise how different types of relationships interact and evolve. This tool is particularly useful in HSNA, where historians need to track the interplay between political, economic, and familial ties across different historical periods.

PK-Clustering: PK-Clustering is a clustering algorithm tailored for historical networks, which often feature overlapping or nested communities Pister, Buono, et al. 2020. This algorithm helps in identifying significant subgroups within the network, such as political factions or religious sects, which can then be further analyzed to understand their role in the broader social structure.

2.2.4 Graph Drawing and Layouts

Graph drawing and layout algorithms are fundamental to the visualisation of networks, particularly in Social Network Analysis (SNA). The positioning of nodes and edges within a visual space significantly affects the ease with which the network structure can be interpreted. Effective layout algorithms enhance the clarity, aesthetics, and interpretability of the network, making them indispensable tools for analyzing complex social structures. The visualisation of social networks often begins with a node-link diagram, where nodes represent entities such as individuals or organisations, and edges represent the relationships between them. Sociograms, developed by Moreno, were among the first examples of such visualisations, depicting friendships between schoolchildren using circles and lines to represent children and their friendship ties,

respectively Moreno 1943. Node link diagrams remain popular because they provide an intuitive and immediately understandable view of small to medium-sized networks. However, as the complexity and size of the network increase, so does the challenge of creating a clear and informative visualisation. The primary objective of a layout algorithm is to position the nodes and edges of the network in such a way that the resulting diagram is both aesthetically pleasing and easy to interpret.

Introduction to Graph Layouts

Graph layout algorithms are mapping functions that assign spatial positions to nodes within a graph. The choice of a graph layout is crucial as it can either reveal or obscure the structural features of the network. A well-chosen layout highlights important aspects such as clusters, hierarchies, or central nodes, while minimizing visual clutter, such as edge crossings, that can detract from the interpretability of the network Zhou et al. 2013. The primary considerations in designing a layout are the aesthetics and readability of the network diagram. These considerations include minimising edge crossings, balancing edge lengths, and optimising the overall area of the diagram as shown in Figure 2.8 Kosak, Marks, and Shieber 1994.

Figure 2.8: Different layout considerations to enhance node-link diagram readability, such as the level of node overlap, the alignment of nodes, or the number of edge crossings. from Kosak, Marks, and Shieber 1994

Layouts can be broadly categorised into several types, including force-directed, hierarchical, circular, grid-based, and clustering layouts. Each type serves a specific purpose and is suited to different kinds of analysis. For example, force-directed layouts are effective in uncovering the community structure within a network, while hierarchical

layouts are ideal for visualising acyclic networks where directional relationships are prominent Schulz, and Schumann 2006.

Force-Directed Layouts: Force-directed layouts are among the most widely used methods for network visualisation. These layouts simulate physical forces to position nodes in a way that reflects the underlying structure of the network. Nodes are treated as repelling charges, while edges are modelled as springs that pull connected nodes together. The layout is achieved by iteratively minimising a potential energy function, thus bringing the network to a state of equilibrium where the nodes that are more closely related are closer to each other, and those less related are farther apart Fruchterman, and Reingold 1991.

The force-directed layout algorithm minimizes an energy function E that can be expressed as:

$$E = \sum_{(i,j) \in E} k_{ij} (\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j\| - d_{ij})^2 + \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i q_j}{\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j\|} \quad (2.17)$$

where:

- E is the total energy of the system.
- k_{ij} is the spring constant for the edge connecting nodes i and j .
- $\|\mathbf{p}_i - \mathbf{p}_j\|$ is the Euclidean distance between nodes i and j .
- d_{ij} is the desired length of the spring, often normalized to 1.
- q_i and q_j are the charges (or repulsion coefficients) of the nodes i and j .

The algorithm adjusts the positions of nodes iteratively using methods like gradient descent until the system reaches a state of minimal energy Kamada, Kawai, et al. 1989. The resulting layout is typically aesthetically pleasing, with minimal edge crossings and a clear representation of clusters within the network. Force-directed layouts are particularly effective for visualising networks where the overall structure and the formation of clusters are of interest. For example, in social networks, force-directed layouts can reveal communities - groups of nodes that are more densely connected than the rest of the network Gilbert et al. 2011. However, these layouts can become computationally expensive as the size of the network increases, and they may produce cluttered visuals if the network is highly connected Venturini, Jacomy, and Jensen 2019.

fCoSE and CoSE Layouts: The fCoSE (Fast Compound Spring Embedder) and CoSE (Compound Spring Embedder) layouts are advanced versions of force-directed layouts designed for compound graphs—graphs that contain nested structures. CoSE and fCoSE extend the basic force-directed model by considering additional constraints and interactions between nodes in different subgraphs. These layouts are particularly useful in visualizing biological networks, software architecture diagrams, or any hierarchical structure where sub-networks are nested within larger networks Dogrusoz, Giral, et al.

2009. These layouts have been implemented in various graph visualisation tools like Cytoscape and Gephi, making them accessible to researchers across disciplines.

Hierarchical Layouts: Hierarchical layouts are designed to represent directed acyclic graphs (DAGs), where nodes are arranged in levels according to their hierarchical relationships. This type of layout is particularly useful for visualising structures such as organisational charts, decision trees, or genealogies, where there is a clear top-down flow of information or influence Sugiyama, Tagawa, and Toda 1981.

In hierarchical layouts, nodes are first assigned to levels based on their depth in the hierarchy, usually determined by a breadth-first search (BFS) starting from the root node. The node ordering within each level is optimized to minimize edge crossings, a problem that is NP-hard and typically addressed using heuristic methods. The positions of nodes are then determined by solving a system of linear equations that balance the trade-offs between minimizing edge crossings and maintaining consistent edge lengths Conn et al. 2017. The Sugiyama Framework is a widely used algorithm for hierarchical layouts. It works by assigning levels to nodes, ordering nodes within each level to minimize edge crossings, and then positioning the nodes to maintain a visually coherent layout. This framework is particularly effective for visualizing hierarchical structures in software engineering, such as class hierarchies or dependency graphs Sugiyama, Tagawa, and Toda 1981.

Hierarchical layouts are ideal for visualizing any network where a clear hierarchy exists. For instance, in genealogical studies, a hierarchical layout can effectively depict family trees, organizing individuals by generations. Similarly, in organizational charts, hierarchical layouts can clearly illustrate reporting structures and chains of command Anand, and Daft 2007.

In chronicle networks, hierarchical layouts have been used to visualize the power structures in medieval societies, where nodes represent individuals or institutions and edges represent feudal ties or vassal relationships Demange 2004. This allows historians to trace the flow of power and influence through different layers of society Kerschbaumer et al. 2020.

Circular and Concentric Layouts: Circular layouts arrange the nodes in a circle, emphasising the symmetry and density of the connections around the central nodes. This layout is particularly useful for networks where relationships between nodes are equally important, with no inherent hierarchy or directional flow.

The positions of the nodes in a circular layout are determined by placing them at equal angular intervals around a circle. The position of each node i in polar coordinates can be expressed as:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = (r \cos(2\pi i/n), r \sin(2\pi i/n)) \quad (2.18)$$

where:

- r is the radius of the circle.

- n is the total number of nodes.
- i is the index of the node.

Concentric Layouts: Concentric layouts are a variation of circular layouts where nodes are arranged in concentric circles based on a given metric, such as centrality. The nodes with the highest centrality are placed in the innermost circle, with other nodes arranged in outer circles based on descending metric values. This layout is particularly effective for highlighting the relative importance of nodes within a network **kim2021visualisation**. Circular and concentric layouts are commonly used in social network analysis to visualise social circles, where each circle represents a different level of proximity or importance. In historical networks, these layouts have been applied to kinship networks, where family members are arranged in concentric circles based on their degree of relatedness to a central figure Lu et al. 2010.

These layouts are also effective in visualizing affiliation networks, where entities are grouped into communities or clusters based on shared attributes or interactions. The concentric layout, in particular, is useful for visualizing networks where centrality metrics, such as betweenness or closeness centrality, are crucial for understanding the network's structure Alzahrani, and Fernstad 2023.

Grid Layouts Grid layouts arrange nodes in a regular grid pattern, which can be useful for comparing multiple networks or subnetworks side by side. This layout is simple but effective for visualising large datasets where uniformity and regular spacing are desirable.

In a grid layout, nodes are positioned on a rectangular grid, with each node assigned a unique grid position. The positions are typically calculated as:

$$\mathbf{p}_i = (x_i, y_i) = (c \cdot \text{floor}(i/r), c \cdot (i \% r)) \quad (2.19)$$

where:

- c is the grid cell size.
- r is the number of rows (or columns, depending on the orientation).
- i is the index of the node.

Grid layouts are particularly useful for visualizing bipartite graphs or for arranging multiple small networks in a comparative study. In the context of historical networks, grid layouts can be used to compare different historical events or periods by placing each event or period in a separate grid cell. This allows historians to systematically analyze and compare the structure of social networks across different contexts or periods Dekker 2000.

Clustering Layouts Clustering layouts are designed to reveal community structures within a network. These layouts group nodes into clusters based on their connectivity and then arrange these clusters to minimize inter-cluster edge crossings and maximize intra-cluster cohesion.

Clustering layouts often use algorithms like k-means clustering or modularity maximization to detect clusters within the network. Once the clusters are identified, the nodes within each cluster are arranged using a force-directed or circular layout, while the clusters themselves are positioned using a higher-level layout strategy, such as a grid or hierarchical layout Tuikkala et al. 2012.

Cise Layouts: The Cise (Circular Layout with Clusters) algorithm is a specialized clustering layout that arranges each cluster in a circle, with clusters themselves arranged using a force-directed approach. This layout is particularly effective for visualizing networks where community structure is a key aspect of the analysis Dogrusoz, Belviranli, and Dilek 2012.

Clustering layouts are widely used in SNA to identify and visualize communities within social networks, such as friend groups, professional networks, or political factions. In historical networks, clustering layouts can reveal how different social, political, or familial groups interacted over time. These layouts are particularly effective in studies that seek to understand the formation and evolution of alliances, rivalries, or other social dynamics in historical contexts Blondel et al. 2008b.

Tree Layouts Tree layouts are essential visualisation techniques in the analysis of complex networks. They are particularly useful in representing hierarchical relationships in historical chronicle networks. These layouts are highly suitable for historical chronicles where temporal and relational hierarchies are prominent. Tree layouts are traditionally used to depict data structures where each node is connected in a parent-child relationship, forming a hierarchical tree. This approach allows for a clear and organized representation of data, which is particularly useful in historical networks where events or entities often follow a lineage or sequence of occurrences Zellweger 2016. The hierarchical nature of tree layouts aligns with the chronological ordering of events, enabling a straightforward interpretation of the flow and connections between historical entities. As explored by Minghim et al. 2020, tree and radial tree layouts are capable of revealing underlying structures and relationships within large and complex datasets by reducing visual clutter and enhancing readability.

Radial tree layouts extend the traditional tree layout by positioning the root node at the centre of the visualisation, with child nodes expanding outward in a circular pattern. This approach is particularly advantageous in scenarios where the goal is to emphasize the centrality of a particular event or entity within the historical network Pádraig MacCarron 2014. The radial tree layout allows for an intuitive understanding of the importance and influence of this central node over the surrounding nodes by placing the most significant node at the centre. This is particularly relevant in historical chronicle networks where certain events or figures are pivotal, and their influence radiates outward, affecting various other events or entities in the network Davison 2019.

2.3 Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a comprehensive review of the literature on gender representation in historical chronicles, with a particular focus on late antique and early medieval sources. It has explored the theoretical frameworks that underpin this research, including feminist historiography and gender studies, which are crucial for understanding the systemic biases that have historically marginalized women in these narratives. In addition, the chapter introduced the key concepts of network analysis and the digital humanities, emphasising their relevance in reevaluating historical texts to uncover overlooked contributions of women.

As we move into Chapters 3 and 4, the discussion will shift towards the methodological approach employed in this research. Chapter 3 will detail the processes of data source selection while chapter 4 will explore network visualisation, and digital analysis techniques used to study the representation of women in the selected historical texts. This transition from theory to methodology is essential to understanding how the innovative digital tools discussed in this chapter are applied in practice to address the research questions posed at the beginning of this thesis.

Chapter 3

Historical Chronicle Data

3.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the research focuses on the careful selection and preparation of datasets crucial for analyzing gender representation within historical chronicles using network visualisation techniques. The process begins with an in-depth exploration of various datasets, emphasizing the importance of selecting sources that provide a comprehensive and accurate portrayal of the social, political, and cultural dynamics of the periods under study. By meticulously choosing datasets from a variety of historical chronicles, this research ensures a robust foundation for subsequent analysis.

The chapter is organized to first introduce the selected datasets, followed by a detailed description of the data preparation and pre-processing steps. Special attention is given to the challenges and limitations inherent in working with historical data, such as its incompleteness or potential biases. These aspects are critical in shaping the interpretation of the networks and the roles of gender within them.

The goal of this chapter is to provide a clear and methodologically sound basis for the network visualisations and analyses presented in the subsequent chapters. By laying out the dataset selection and preparation process in detail, this chapter establishes the reliability and validity of the research findings, particularly in the context of gender representation in historical social networks.

3.2 Dataset Selection

The selection of appropriate datasets is a critical step in any research project, particularly in the context of historical analysis. This section details the data sets chosen for this study, the rationale behind their selection, and the limitations associated with these choices.

3.2.1 Dataset Descriptions and Metadata

The datasets used in this research are derived from a collection of historical chronicles, each containing detailed records of events, individuals, and interactions. These chronicles are invaluable resources for understanding the social, political, and cultural dynamics of the past. The datasets include:

Cassiodorus.csv: This dataset is based on the writings of *Cassiodorus*, a Roman statesman and writer who chronicled the history of the Gothic kingdoms. The dataset includes records of significant individuals, their roles, and their interactions within the Gothic and Roman political spheres.

Marcellinus.csv: Derived from the *Chronicle of Marcellinus Comes*, this dataset focuses on the late Roman Empire, capturing the transition to the Byzantine period. It includes records of emperors, military leaders, and key events that shaped the late antique world.

Hydatius.csv: This dataset is based on the *Chronicle of Hydatius*, a Galician bishop who documented the collapse of the Roman Empire in the West. It provides insights into the social and political upheavals of the time, including interactions between Roman and barbarian groups.

Eusebius-Jerome.csv: This dataset combines the *Chronicle of Eusebius*, a church historian, with the continuation by *Jerome*, providing a comprehensive view of early Christian history and the transformation of the Roman world.

IsidoreMI.csv and IsidoreMA.csv: These datasets are derived from the works of *Isidore of Seville*, a scholar and bishop who documented the history of the Visigoths and the wider Roman world. They capture the cultural and intellectual transitions during the early Middle Ages.

Prosper.csv: This dataset is based on the *Chronicle of Prosper of Aquitaine*, which covers the early medieval period, focusing on the decline of the Western Roman Empire and the rise of barbarian kingdoms.

BedeTransformed.csv: Derived from *Bede's Chronica maiora* or Chapter 66 of *De temporum ratione*, an Anglo-Saxon monk, this dataset chronicles the early history of Britain, including the spread of Christianity and the interactions between different peoples.

fWhitelock.csv: This dataset is based on textitDorothy Whitelock’s *The Beginnings of English Society*, first published in 1952. Her work focused on Anglo-Saxon England. It includes records of kings, queens, and other significant figures in early English history.

Table 3.1 provides a brief overview of the datasets employed in this study. Each dataset is structured to include various attributes that are relevant for network analysis. The metadata in Table 3.2 shows that each entry includes the name of the individual or group, the associated book and chapter (if applicable), year count, gender, whether the individual is named or unnamed, group classification, ethnicity, status, life cycle stage, and various contextual details such as location, motivation, and Latin text references. Connections between individuals are also recorded and classified as positive, negative, neutral, or supernatural.

Dataset	Nodes	Male	Female	Genderless	Unknown	Others	Edges
<i>newBede.csv</i>	1483	1159	68	29	0	227	1489
<i>Eusebius-Jerome.csv</i>	4222	3272	162	142	0	646	4228
<i>BedeForSam.csv</i>	1483	1159	68	29	0	227	1483
<i>Prosper.csv</i>	3051	2717	78	35	0	221	3058
<i>Hydatius.csv</i>	676	578	27	9	0	62	676
<i>IsidoreMA.csv</i>	726	548	23	55	0	100	732
<i>Cassiodorus.csv</i>	3041	2970	16	10	0	45	3041
<i>IsidoreMI.csv</i>	290	246	7	10	0	27	296
<i>Marcellinus.csv</i>	1180	1042	57	3	0	78	1181
<i>f_Whitelock.csv</i>	1869	1266	108	48	62	385	1869

Table 3.1: Summary of Datasets Excluding Specific Nodes

3.2.2 Choice of Datasets

The selection of the data sets for this research was informed by several key considerations that align with the study objectives of analysing gender roles within historical chronicles and historical accounts. First, the diversity of sources was a primary factor. The data sets represent a broad spectrum of historical texts from different geographical regions, periods, and cultural contexts. This diversity is critical for a comprehensive examination of gender roles, as it allows the study to encompass a wide range of social, political, and cultural dynamics. By including chronicles from various parts of Europe and spanning different centuries, the analysis is better positioned to uncover patterns that are consistent across time and place, as well as those that are unique to specific contexts.

Another important consideration was the richness of the data within each dataset. The selected chronicles provide detailed accounts of individuals and their interactions, offering a wealth of information that is crucial for network analysis. This richness facilitates the identification of complex patterns and relationships that might not be evident in less detailed records. For example, the depth of information allows the study to trace connections between individuals, understand the nature of these connections,

and assess how these relationships may have influenced historical events or societal structures. The detailed accounts of interactions and roles within these chronicles make them particularly valuable for this type of analysis.

The representation of gender within these datasets was another critical factor. The chronicles included in this study explicitly reference gender, which is essential for analysing the roles and representations of women in historical records. This gender-related metadata is crucial for addressing the research questions, as it allows for a focused analysis of how women were portrayed and how their roles were recorded (or not recorded) in these historical texts. The explicit inclusion of gender data helps ensure that the analysis can directly address issues of underrepresentation and bias in historical narratives.

Finally, the availability of metadata was considered in the selection of datasets. The chosen chronicles include detailed metadata for each entry, including connections between individuals, their social status, ethnicity, life cycle stage, and more. This metadata enriches the quality of the network analysis by providing context for relationships within the network. The metadata allows for a more nuanced interpretation of the data, enabling the analysis to go beyond surface-level observations and delve into the underlying dynamics of historical interactions.

Column	Description
A, Name	Individual or group name
B, Book	Book number (if applicable)
C, Chapter	Chapter number (if applicable)
D, Year count	Year number (for chronicles)
E, Gender	Gender: M = male, F = female, X = genderless, V = mixed, U = unknown
F, Named/Unnamed	N = named, U = unnamed (write name if identifiable)
G, Group	I = individual, G = group
H, Ethnicity	Ethnicity (if available)
I, Status	Social status (e.g., king, bishop)
J, Life cycle	P = 0-14, I = 14-49, S = 49+ (if known)
K, When	When it occurred
L, Where	Where it occurred
M, Why	Reason it occurred
N, Latin text	Relevant Latin text (if applicable)
O, Notes	Additional notes
P onwards, Connections	Connections recorded as names from Column A
	Positive connections: Family ties, marriages, etc.
	Negative connections: Hostile interactions
	Neutral connections: Connections that aren't positive or negative
	Post mortem/supernatural connections: Connections with angels, demons, or deceased saints

Table 3.2: Metadata Structure for the Dataset

3.2.3 Limitations

While the datasets chosen for this study offer many advantages, several limitations must be acknowledged. One of the primary limitations is the bias in historical records. The chronicles from which these datasets are derived were often written by male authors who reflected the societal biases of their time. As a result, the representation of women and other marginalized groups in these records may be incomplete or skewed. This bias can affect the analysis by limiting the visibility of women's roles in history, thereby reinforcing the very under-representation that this study seeks to address.

Another limitation is the incomplete nature of the data. In some instances, the data sets may lack information on certain individuals or events. This incompleteness could be due to various reasons, such as gaps in the original record, loss of data over time, or selective data collection recording practices. These gaps can limit the scope of the analysis, as they may obscure important connections or events that could have been critical to understanding the historical context.

The ambiguity in metadata also poses challenges. In certain cases, the metadata associated with an entry may be ambiguous or difficult to interpret, especially when dealing with unnamed individuals or groups. This ambiguity can complicate the network analysis, as it can require the researcher to make interpretive decisions that could influence the results. For example, determining the exact nature of a connection between two individuals based on vague or incomplete metadata may introduce a level of subjectivity into the analysis.

Lastly, there are temporal and spatial limitations associated with the datasets. The chronicles included in this study are focused on specific periods and regions, which may limit the reliability of the findings. While the selected chronicles provide rich insights into their respective contexts, they may not fully capture the diversity of gender roles across different historical settings. This limitation means that while the study can offer valuable insights into the chronicles analyzed, its findings may not be entirely applicable to other historical contexts outside the scope of the selected datasets.

3.3 Data Preparation and Pre-processing

The data preparation and pre-processing steps were essential for ensuring that the dataset, sourced from historical chronicles as detailed in the previous section of this thesis, was ready for accurate analysis and visualisation. The data were collected from various chronicle sources highlighted before. This included names, gender identifiers, life stages, and various types of connections between entities. Given the complexity and variability of the historical data, it was necessary to implement rigorous cleaning and preprocessing procedures to standardise and refine the data set as shown in Appendix A Algorithm 5 and Code 6.1.

The initial data preparation involved handling various inconsistencies inherent in the historical data. Firstly, we systematically processed each row of the dataset, focusing on critical fields such as names, gender identifiers, and relational connections. Key tasks

included trimming unnecessary spaces from text entries, converting all gender identifiers to uppercase for consistency, and ensuring that fields like "Named/Unnamed" and "Life cycle" were uniformly categorized. The script also identified and grouped columns that contained similar or duplicated information, consolidating these entries to avoid redundancy. For example, names that appeared under different labels were combined into a single consistent representation, which helped maintain the integrity of the network analysis.

Furthermore, the pre-processing involved filtering out irrelevant data that did not contribute meaningful information to the analysis. Specifically, rows that only indicated an age or period (e.g., "First Age", "Second Age") without additional context were removed. This step ensured that the dataset focused on relevant entities and relationships. We also addressed edge cases, such as unexpected or malformed data entries in gender or named fields, by either correcting these inconsistencies or flagging them for further review.

The combination of these preprocessing efforts provided a robust foundation for the network analysis. By thoroughly preparing the data, the analysis could accurately represent the complex relationships and gender dynamics within the historical chronicles, offering new insights into the societal structures of the past.

3.4 Chapter Summary

This chapter has provided a comprehensive overview of the datasets used in this thesis to analyze gender representation within historical chronicles. The chapter began with a detailed discussion of the criteria for selecting relevant historical chronicles, ensuring that the chosen sources offer a diverse and accurate depiction of social dynamics during the late antique and early medieval periods.

This chapter also addressed the significant challenges inherent in working with historical data, such as issues related to data completeness, biases, and the interpretive difficulties that arise from these factors. These challenges were mitigated through careful data preparation and preprocessing, which included steps like cleaning the data, standardizing names and relationships, and ensuring that the datasets were suitable for network analysis.

Finally, this chapter provides a background necessary to design the methodological framework for constructing and analyzing the gendered networks within these chronicles. This involves defining the network structures, selecting appropriate centrality measures, and employing community detection algorithms to uncover patterns and relationships that might otherwise remain hidden. By establishing a rigorous approach to data selection and preparation, this chapter has set the stage for the in-depth network analyses that follow in the next chapter, providing a solid foundation for exploring the complexities of gender dynamics in historical narratives.

Chapter 4

Methodology

4.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodological framework employed in this research, focussing on how gender roles are represented and analysed within historical chronicles using network visualisation and digital analysis. The chapter is structured into several key sections, beginning with an in-depth discussion of network visualisation techniques, including network definition, centrality calculations, and community detection followed by network layouts employed. Further, we, discuss gender representation, including the choices of node shapes, colours, and connections, which are crucial to enhancing the clarity and interpretability of visualisations. The chapter concludes with a discussion of the tools used for analysis, providing a foundation for the findings and discussion presented in subsequent chapters.

4.2 Network Visualisation

Network visualisation serves as a crucial method for interpreting and understanding complex datasets, especially in the context of historical chronicles. Through network visualisation, intricate relationships between individuals or groups can be elucidated, revealing patterns and structures that are otherwise difficult to discern. In this section, we will delve into the specifics of how networks are defined, how centrality and community structures are identified, and the choices made in terms of network layouts to enhance the interpretability of the data.

4.2.1 Network Definition

A network, mathematically referred to as a graph, is a set of entities known as nodes (or vertices) and the relationships between them, known as edges. In this study, we define our network $G = (V, E)$, where V represents the set of nodes, and E represents the set of edges. Nodes in our context correspond to individuals or groups recorded in

historical chronicles, while edges represent the interactions or relationships between these entities.

Nodes: Each node $v \in V$ in the network corresponds to a unique individual or group as captured in the dataset. These nodes are not merely points on a graph but are imbued with attributes that describe them. Attributes include gender, named/unnamed status, group classification (whether the node represents an individual or a collective group), ethnicity, societal status (such as king, bishop, etc.), and life cycle stage (such as *pueritia*, *iuuentus*, or *senectus*). These attributes provide critical context for the network analysis, allowing for a more nuanced interpretation of the relationships within the historical data.

Edges: Edges $e \in E$ in the network denote the relationships between nodes. These edges can be either directed or undirected, depending on the nature of the interaction they represent. For instance, a directed edge might signify a one-way relationship such as a command or a letter, whereas an undirected edge could represent a mutual relationship like a marriage or alliance. Furthermore, edges are categorized based on the nature of the interaction—positive (e.g., alliances or friendships), negative (e.g., conflicts or rivalries), neutral (e.g., interactions that are neither explicitly positive nor negative), or supernatural (e.g., interactions involving angels or deceased individuals). The weight of an edge may reflect the strength or frequency of the interaction, thus capturing the intensity or importance of the relationship in the historical context.

The network can be represented mathematically using an adjacency matrix A , where each element $A_{ij} = 1$ if there is an edge from node i to node j , and $A_{ij} = 0$ otherwise. In the case of weighted networks, the matrix A would take on values corresponding to the weight of the edges, thereby encoding the strength of the connections between nodes.

Appendix B Code 6.2 provides the implementation of this approach for network design. Visualising the network involves using different layouts that optimise the positioning of nodes and edges to improve clarity and understanding. These visualisations are not just for aesthetic purposes but are carefully chosen to highlight specific aspects of the data, such as the centrality of certain nodes or the clustering of groups. Using these visualisations, the structure and dynamics within the historical chronicles become more accessible, allowing for insights that may not be immediately apparent from the raw data alone.

4.2.2 Centrality Calculations

Centrality measures are a fundamental aspect of network analysis, offering a way to quantify the importance or influence of nodes within the network. In this study, three key centrality measures are calculated: degree centrality, closeness centrality, and betweenness centrality. Each of these measures provides a different perspective on the importance of the node.

Degree Centrality: Degree centrality $C_D(v)$ is perhaps the most straightforward centrality measure. It is defined as the number of edges connected to a node v . This measure provides a basic indication of a node's connectivity within the network. Nodes

with a high degree of centrality are those that have many direct connections to other nodes, suggesting that they play a prominent role in the network. Mathematically, degree centrality is calculated as:

$$C_D(v) = \deg(v) = \sum_{u \in V} A_{uv} \quad (4.1)$$

where $\deg(v)$ is the degree of node v , and A_{uv} is the entry in the adjacency matrix corresponding to the edge between nodes u and v . Nodes with a high degree of centrality are likely to be key players in the historical narrative, either due to their influence or their involvement in numerous interactions.

Closeness Centrality: Closeness centrality $C_C(v)$ measures how close a node is to all other nodes in the network. It is the reciprocal of the sum of the shortest path distances from v to all other nodes. This measure reflects how quickly information or influence can spread from a given node to the rest of the network. Nodes with high closeness centrality are those that are centrally located within the network, making them potentially crucial for the dissemination of information or coordinating actions. The formula for closeness centrality is:

$$C_C(v) = \frac{1}{\sum_{u \in V} d(v, u)} \quad (4.2)$$

where $d(v, u)$ is the shortest path distance between nodes v and u . In the context of historical chronicles, nodes with high centrality of closeness can represent individuals who had significant influence or who were pivotal in maintaining communication between different groups. The algorithm 2 shows the implementation of the closeness centrality using the A* algorithm in our work. The A* algorithm stated in algorithm 1 is chosen for its efficiency in finding the shortest path by combining heuristic and actual cost, making it particularly well-suited for applications in network analysis where optimal pathfinding is crucial Hart, Nilsson, and Raphael 1968. As highlighted in recent studies Zhao, Liang, and J. Wang 2021 This balance between exploration and exploitation reduces computational overhead, ensuring precise and timely results.

Betweenness Centrality: Betweenness centrality $C_B(v)$ quantifies the number of times a node acts as a bridge along the shortest path between two other nodes. This measure identifies nodes that play a crucial role in the flow of information or resources within the network. Nodes with high betweenness centrality are often gatekeepers or brokers, controlling access between different parts of the network. The mathematical expression for betweenness centrality is:

$$C_B(v) = \sum_{s \neq v \neq t} \frac{\sigma_{st}(v)}{\sigma_{st}} \quad (4.3)$$

where σ_{st} is the total number of shortest routes from node s to node t , and $\sigma_{st}(v)$ is the number of paths that pass through node v . In historical contexts, nodes with high betweenness centrality could correspond to individuals who were key intermediaries, perhaps facilitating alliances or serving as conduits for communication. Algorithm 3

Algorithm 1 A* Algorithm for Shortest Path

Require: Graph $G = (V, E)$, start node s , goal node g **Ensure:** Shortest path from s to g

```

1: Initialize open set  $O \leftarrow \{s\}$ 
2: Initialize closed set  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3: Initialize  $gScore(s) \leftarrow 0$ 
4: Initialize  $fScore(s) \leftarrow$  heuristic estimate from  $s$  to  $g$ 
5: while  $O$  is not empty do
6:    $current \leftarrow$  node in  $O$  with lowest  $fScore$ 
7:   if  $current = g$  then
8:     return reconstruct path from  $g$  to  $s$ 
9:   end if
10:  Remove  $current$  from  $O$ 
11:  Add  $current$  to  $C$ 
12:  for each neighbor  $n$  of  $current$  do
13:    if  $n \in C$  then
14:      continue
15:    end if
16:    tentative_gScore  $\leftarrow gScore(current) + edge\_cost(current, n)$ 
17:    if  $n \notin O$  then
18:      Add  $n$  to  $O$ 
19:    else if tentative_gScore  $\geq gScore(n)$  then
20:      continue
21:    end if
22:     $gScore(n) \leftarrow tentative\_gScore$ 
23:     $fScore(n) \leftarrow gScore(n) +$  heuristic estimate from  $n$  to  $g$ 
24:  end for
25: end while
26: return failure ▷ No path found

```

Algorithm 2 Closeness Centrality Using A* Algorithm**Require:** Graph $G = (V, E)$, current node v **Ensure:** Closeness centrality $C_C(v)$ of node v

```

1: Initialize  $total\_distance \leftarrow 0$ 
2: Initialize  $nodes \leftarrow$  set of all nodes in  $G$ 
3: Initialize  $nodeId \leftarrow v.id$ 
4: Initialize  $closeness \leftarrow 0$ 
5: for each node  $n \in nodes$  do
6:   if  $n.id \neq nodeId$  then
7:      $aStarResult \leftarrow$  A* search from  $v$  to  $n$   $\triangleright$  Run A* algorithm between
       nodes  $v$  and  $n$ 
8:     if  $aStarResult.found$  then
9:        $total\_distance \leftarrow total\_distance + aStarResult.distance$ 
10:    end if
11:  end if
12: end for
13: return  $closeness \leftarrow \frac{1}{total\_distance}$   $\triangleright$  Closeness centrality is the inverse of
    total distance

```

provides the implementation of betweenness centrality used in this study using the A* algorithm for finding the shortest paths.

4.2.3 Community Detection

Community detection is a method used to identify groups of nodes within a network that are more densely connected than the rest of the network. In this study, community detection is used to uncover subgroups within the historical chronicles, potentially revealing factions, alliances, or other forms of social or political organization.

The method implemented in our study utilizes Connected Component Labeling (CCL) or Component Identification to identify and label distinct connected subgraphs within a larger network Fu, Chen, and Gao 2009. In graph theory, a connected component is defined as a maximal subgraph where every pair of nodes is connected by a path, and no additional nodes from outside this subgraph can be connected without violating this property West 2001.

Given an undirected graph $G = (V, E)$, where V is the set of nodes (vertices) and E is the set of edges connecting them, the connected component labelling process identifies subgraphs C within G . Each subgraph C consists of nodes V_C such that any pair of nodes in V_C are connected by a path, and C is maximal in the sense that no additional nodes from $V \setminus V_C$ can be added without violating the connectivity. The algorithm as shown in algorithm 4 operates by iterating through each node in the graph, and for any unvisited node, it initiates a traversal (either Depth-First Search (DFS) or Breadth-First Search (BFS)) to explore and mark all reachable nodes, grouping them into a single

Algorithm 3 Betweenness Centrality Calculation using A* Algorithm

```

1: Input: Graph  $G = (V, E)$ , Node  $v \in V$ 
2: Output: Betweenness centrality  $C_B(v)$ 
3:  $C_B(v) \leftarrow 0$  ▷ Initialize betweenness centrality for node  $v$ 
4: for each node  $s \in V$  do ▷ Iterate over all source nodes
5:   for each node  $t \in V$  do ▷ Iterate over all target nodes
6:     if  $s \neq t$  and  $s \neq v$  and  $t \neq v$  then
7:        $aStarResult \leftarrow A^*(s, t, G)$  ▷ Run A* algorithm from  $s$  to  $t$ 
8:       if  $aStarResult.found$  then
9:          $shortestPath \leftarrow aStarResult.path$ 
10:        if  $v \in shortestPath$  then
11:           $C_B(v) \leftarrow C_B(v) + \frac{1}{length(shortestPath)}$  ▷ Update betweenness
centrality
12:        end if
13:      end if
14:    end if
15:  end for
16: end for
17: return  $C_B(v)$  ▷ Return the calculated betweenness centrality

```

component.

Mathematically, the complexity of this method is $O(V + E)$, where V represents the number of vertices and E the number of edges. This time complexity is linear and makes the approach particularly efficient for large, sparse graphs, where a quick identification of isolated communities is necessary. The simplicity of this algorithm ensures that it effectively traverses the entire graph, visiting each node exactly once and marking all components without redundant operations.

This method is especially beneficial for visualizing and distinguishing isolated subgroups within large networks. By colouring or labelling each connected component distinctly, it provides a clear and intuitive representation of the network's organization, making the internal structure of the graph immediately apparent. While connected component labelling is ideal for non-overlapping communities, it does not consider the internal structure or density variations within each component. Therefore, for more complex community detection tasks—where communities may overlap or where internal cohesiveness is important—more advanced methods such as the Louvain algorithm or modularity-based approaches are recommended Blondel et al. 2008a. Nonetheless, connected component labelling remains a valuable tool in community detection due to its computational efficiency and clarity, especially when dealing with large datasets. In historical analysis, the detection of communities can highlight significant social or political divisions, such as rival factions or groups that collaborated closely. These insights can provide a deeper understanding of the underlying dynamics within the

Algorithm 4 Connected Component Labeling

```
1: Input: Graph  $G = (V, E)$ 
2: Output: List of connected components
3: Initialize visited[V] to False for all  $v \in V$ 
4: Initialize components as an empty list
5: for each node  $v \in V$  do
6:   if visited[v] is False then
7:     Initialize a new empty component  $C$ 
8:     Perform DFS or BFS starting from  $v$ 
9:     for each node  $u$  found during the traversal do
10:      Mark visited[u] as True
11:      Add  $u$  to component  $C$ 
12:     end for
13:     Add component  $C$  to components list
14:   end if
15: end for
16: return components
```

chronicles, revealing the hidden structure of historical relationships.

4.2.4 Network Layouts and Exploration

The choice of network layouts is critical for effective visualisation and interpretation, particularly in a study that deals with the intricate relationships and structures found in historical chronicles. Different layouts serve different purposes, highlighting various aspects of the network, such as centrality, clustering, or the overall geometric shape of the network. Each layout is selected to provide specific insights into the data, making it easier to explore and interpret the complex relationships captured in the historical narratives.

FCoSE layout: The Force-Directed Compound Spring Embedder (FCoSE) layout is a sophisticated force-directed layout designed for visualizing networks that contain hierarchical structures. This layout operates on the principle of balancing attractive and repulsive forces between nodes, similar to how physical objects interact Cytoscape.org 2024. Nodes that are connected by an edge experience an attractive force pulling them closer together, while all nodes experience a repulsive force pushing them apart. The result is a visually appealing and informative layout that naturally highlights central nodes and clusters. This layout is particularly effective in historical networks, where hierarchical relationships, such as those between rulers and subjects or between different social strata, need to be delineated.

CiSE Layout: The Circular Spring Embedder (CiSE) layout is specifically designed to emphasize clusters or communities within the network. It arranges nodes in a circular

pattern, with clusters of nodes placed within separate circles. This layout is especially useful for identifying and visualizing community structures within the network, making it easier to interpret the relationships within each community Dogrusoz, Belviranlı, and Dilek 2012. For example, in a historical network, CiSE might be used to delineate different factions or alliances, allowing researchers to see how tightly-knit certain groups were, and how they interacted with other communities. The circular arrangement also aids in comparing the relative sizes and densities of different communities, providing insights into their influence and connectivity within the broader network.

Concentric Layout: The Concentric layout organises nodes in a series of concentric circles based on their distance from a central node or group of nodes. This layout is particularly effective for visualizing the hierarchical structure of a network, such as the relationships between a central figure and its connections. For example, in a medieval network, the king or queen might be placed at the centre, with their immediate advisors and family members in the innermost circle, followed by lesser nobles and subjects in outer circles. This layout not only emphasises the centrality of certain figures within the network but also makes it easy to see the levels of influence and proximity to power that different individuals or groups had.

Radial Tree Layout (Breadthfirst): The Radial Tree layout, using a breadth-first approach, organizes nodes in a tree-like structure that radiates outward from a central node. This layout is particularly effective for visualizing hierarchical relationships, such as genealogies or organizational structures, where a central figure or concept is the root, and all other nodes branch outwards in levels. In the context of historical analysis, this layout could be used to map out the influential or central nodes in the chronicle network. Structuring the network in this way helps us explore the central character on whom the narratives revolve.

Circular Layout: In the circular layout, nodes are arranged in a circle, equidistant from each other. This layout is often used when the focus is on showing the equivalence or symmetry of nodes, as it visually places all nodes on equal footing. It is particularly useful when the goal is to emphasise the relationships among the nodes rather than their hierarchy or centrality. For instance, in a historical context, this layout might be used to depict the relationships among a group of peers or equals, such as members of a council or alliance, where the focus is on their interactions rather than on a strict power hierarchy.

Grid Layout: The Grid layout arranges nodes in a regular, grid-like pattern. This layout is less concerned with reflecting the natural structure of the network and more about organising the nodes in a systematic and orderly way for clarity. The Grid layout is particularly useful when dealing with large datasets, as it allows for the presentation of a large number of nodes in an organized manner, although it may obscure the true relationships between nodes. For example, this layout might be used to display all individuals mentioned in a chronicle in an orderly fashion, making it easy to find and identify specific individuals, even if the connections between them are less visually apparent.

Random Layout: The Random layout places nodes randomly within the visualisa-

tion space, without any particular regard to their relationships or hierarchical structure. While this layout doesn't provide much structural insight, it can be useful for comparing the effects of different layouts or for initializing more sophisticated layout algorithms. The Random layout can serve as a baseline or starting point, helping to illustrate the effectiveness of other, more structured layouts by providing a contrast to them.

Cose-Bilkent (Force-Directed): The Cose-Bilkent layout is a variant of the force-directed layout algorithm, widely used for its ability to produce aesthetically pleasing visualisations that accurately reflect the underlying structure of the network. In this layout, nodes repel each other, while edges act like springs pulling connected nodes together. This balance between attractive and repulsive forces results in a layout that effectively displays the overall structure of the network while maintaining the clarity of individual connections. This layout is particularly useful in historical networks where the relationships between entities are complex and multi-faceted, as it allows for a clear and intuitive representation of these connections.

Spread (Radial Force-Directed): The Spread layout is another force-directed layout but with an added radial constraint. It is designed to highlight the centrality and spread of nodes from a central point. This layout is particularly effective for networks where the central node or nodes have many connections radiating outward, making it easier to see which nodes are at the periphery versus those closer to the core. In a historical context, this layout could be used to visualise the influence of a central figure or group, showing how their connections spread across the network and identifying which individuals or groups are more peripheral.

Cola (Bundled): The Cola layout employs edge bundling, a technique particularly useful for reducing visual clutter in networks with many edges. By grouping similar edges, this layout allows for a clearer view of the overall structure and the main connections within the network. This is especially important in dense networks where individual connections can be hard to distinguish. In historical networks, where numerous relationships and interactions are recorded, the Cola layout helps to simplify the visualisation, making it easier to identify key connections and patterns without being overwhelmed by the sheer volume of data.

These layouts are chosen for their ability to highlight different aspects of the network, making it easier to explore and interpret the complex relationships captured in the historical chronicles. By applying these various layouts, researchers can gain multiple perspectives on the same data, helping to uncover insights that might not be visible with a single-layout approach. The choice of layout depends on the specific aspect of the network that needs to be emphasized, whether it's the hierarchical structure, the clustering of communities, or the centrality of key nodes.

4.3 Gender Representation

Gender representation is a critical aspect of this study, as it directly addresses the research questions on the roles and representations of women in historical chronicles. In network visualisation, choices about how gender is represented can significantly

impact the interpretability and clarity of the visualisations. This section discusses the choices made for node shapes, node colours, and connections based on gender, and how these choices contribute to the overall analysis.

4.3.1 Choice of Node Shape

In network visualisation, node shape is a powerful tool for distinguishing between different categories of data Becker, Eick, and Wilks 1995. For this study, geometric node shapes as shown in Figure 4.1 were chosen to represent gender in a way that is intuitive and easily recognizable, ensuring that the visualisation remains clear and accessible as explored by Cabric et al. 2023.

Circle (Male): The circle shape is used to represent male individuals. This choice is grounded in traditional symbolisms often found in historical contexts, where rounded shapes can denote continuity and strength. The ellipse, being smooth and continuous, reflects these characteristics, making it an appropriate choice for representing male nodes. The use of an ellipse for males aligns with conventional representations and ensures that the visual distinction is immediately apparent, helping viewers quickly identify male individuals within the network.

Triangle (Female): The triangle shape is used to represent female individuals. The triangle's pointed shape can be seen as a symbol of focus and direction, perhaps reflecting the historically significant but often underrepresented roles of women. The triangle, with its sharp angles and distinct shape, contrasts with the ellipse, making it easy to differentiate female nodes from male ones. The use of a triangle helps to mark female individuals within the network, allowing for the identification of gender-related patterns and disparities in historical records.

Diamond (Genderless): A diamond shape is used for entities that are considered genderless, such as angels or spirits. The diamond, with its equal-sided structure, symbolizes balance and neutrality, making it an appropriate choice for representing genderless entities that don't conform to traditional gender norms. This shape stands out from the others, signalling to the viewer that these nodes represent something different—entities that operate outside the conventional gender binaries of male and female.

Square (Other/Undefined): For nodes where the gender is undefined or does not fit into the standard categories, a square shape is used. The square, with its even sides, provides a neutral and non-biased representation of these entities, ensuring that they are visually distinct from those with defined gender roles. The use of a square for undefined or other genders allows for a clear and systematic approach to categorizing nodes, ensuring that all entities are represented in a way that is both consistent and easily interpretable.

These shape choices are not arbitrary but are carefully designed to enhance the clarity of the network visualisation. By assigning distinct shapes to different genders, the visualisation becomes more interpretable, allowing researchers to quickly identify gender-related patterns and anomalies within the network and making it easier to draw

meaningful conclusions about the roles and representations of different genders in historical chronicles. These shape choices contribute to a more nuanced understanding of how gender roles are distributed and how they interact within the broader network.

Node Shapes and Colour Codes

Figure 4.1: Node shapes and colour codes used in this study

4.3.2 Choice of Node Colors

"Color is one of the most powerful tools for communication in visualisation, encoding information quickly and effectively."

— *Maureen Stone, A Field Guide to Digital Color*¹

Colour is one of the most effective visual tools in network visualisation for encoding complex information. In this study, the choice of colours for nodes is particularly important, as it helps to differentiate between genders and enhances the overall visual clarity of the network. The colours are chosen not only for their aesthetic appeal but also for their symbolic associations and their ability to stand out within the visual context of the network Cabric et al. 2023.

Orange (Male): The colour orange is used to represent male nodes. Orange is a vibrant and warm colour, often associated with energy and vitality. It is chosen for male nodes because it stands out well against most backgrounds, ensuring that these nodes are easily visible within the network. By using orange, the visualisation avoids the traditional blue colour typically associated with males, thus offering a modern and unbiased representation. This choice also ensures that male nodes are distinguishable

¹Stone 2003

from other gender categories, aiding in the identification of gender-based patterns and interactions.

Green (Female): Green is chosen to represent female nodes. Green is commonly associated with growth, vitality, and nature, which can symbolically represent the nurturing and essential roles that women have historically played. It contrasts well with the orange used for male nodes, ensuring that the two genders are easily distinguishable from one another. The use of green for female nodes is a deliberate choice to break away from traditional gender colour stereotypes, providing a fresh and meaningful representation that aligns with the study's goals of highlighting the often overlooked roles of women in historical narratives.

Purple Hue (Genderless): A purple hue is used for genderless nodes, such as those representing supernatural entities or spirits. Purple is often associated with spirituality, mystery, and the otherworldly, making it a fitting choice for these nodes. The use of purple helps to set these nodes apart from those representing gendered individuals, emphasizing their unique status within the network. The distinctiveness of purple in the visual spectrum ensures that genderless nodes are immediately recognizable, helping to draw attention to the roles of these entities in the network.

Yellow (Various): Yellow is used to represent nodes that denote groups with mixed genders. Yellow is bright, attention-grabbing, and often associated with diversity and inclusivity. This colour choice ensures that mixed-gender groups are easily identifiable within the network. By using yellow, the visualisation highlights the presence and significance of these diverse groups, allowing for a more comprehensive analysis of how mixed-gender entities function within the historical context.

Red (Unknown): Red is used for nodes where the gender is unknown. Red is a strong, noticeable colour often associated with alertness and caution. Its use in this context serves to draw attention to nodes where gender information is missing or ambiguous, prompting further investigation or consideration during the analysis. The choice of red helps to visually flag these nodes, ensuring that they are not overlooked in the broader analysis of gender representation within the network.

These colour choices play a crucial role in enhancing the visual appeal of the network and making it more functional as a research tool. By thoughtfully applying these colours, the network visualisation becomes an effective medium for analyzing gender representation in historical chronicles. The use of colour not only helps to distinguish between different gender categories but also adds depth to the analysis, allowing researchers to explore gender dynamics with greater precision and insight.

4.3.3 Choice of Connections

The visual representation of connections, or edges, between nodes is another critical aspect of network visualisation. In this study, edges are not only used to denote relationships between nodes but are also colour-coded and styled based on the nature of these relationships. This approach helps to convey the complexity of interactions within the network and makes it easier to interpret the underlying historical data.

Blue (Positive Interactions): Positive interactions, such as alliances, friendships, or supportive relationships, are represented by blue edges. Blue is often associated with trust, loyalty, and calm, making it an ideal colour for denoting positive relationships within the network. The use of blue for positive interactions helps to visually reinforce the constructive and beneficial nature of these connections, making them stand out in the network and aid in the analysis of supportive social structures.

Red (Negative Interactions): Negative interactions, such as conflicts, rivalries, or enmities, are represented by red edges. Red, a colour commonly associated with danger, conflict, and urgency, is appropriate for highlighting antagonistic relationships. Using red, the visualisation signals the presence of discord or opposition within the network, helping researchers quickly identify and focus on areas of conflict or tension within the historical narrative.

Grey (Neutral Interactions): Neutral interactions, which are neither explicitly positive nor negative, are represented by grey edges. Grey, being a neutral and subdued colour, effectively conveys the lack of a clear emotional or relational tone in these interactions. The use of grey for neutral connections ensures that they are visually distinct from both positive and negative interactions, providing a balanced representation of interactions that may be more transactional or indifferent.

Green (Supernatural Interactions): Interactions involving supernatural entities, such as angels or spirits, are represented by green edges. Green's association with the mystical and otherworldly makes it a fitting choice for these types of connections, distinguishing them from more mundane interactions. The use of green for supernatural interactions helps to highlight the unique and often symbolic roles that these entities play within the historical network, adding a layer of analysis to the study.

By visually encoding the type of connection through colour and style, the network visualisation becomes a richer, more informative tool for exploring historical narratives. These choices in edge colours and styles help to convey the complexity of relationships within the network, providing users with the ability to quickly discern the nature of the interactions between different entities. This approach enhances the interpretability of the network and allows for a more nuanced understanding of the dynamics at play within the historical chronicles.

4.3.4 Case Studies

To validate and explore the methodologies and visualisations described in this chapter it is essential to conduct a comparative analysis with existing tools that have been discussed in the literature. This approach will provide a comprehensive evaluation of our tool's capabilities while also situating it within the broader landscape of visual analytics tools used in historical and gender studies.

Historically, various tools have been developed to analyze social networks within historical chronicles, each with its strengths and limitations. For instance, VAIroma, discussed by Cho et al. 2015, integrates text analysis with spatial and temporal visualizations to explore Roman history. Although this tool provides valuable insights into

the connections between events and locations, it does not specifically focus on gender representation. Similarly, the work of Pádraig MacCarron 2014 on Icelandic sagas using network analysis provides a framework for understanding social structures but lacks features that specifically address the visualisation of gendered interactions.

In this study, we will compare our tool with these and other tools discussed in Chapter 2, focussing on several key criteria: the ability to highlight gendered networks, the flexibility of network manipulation, and the tool's usability in exploring complex social structures. By examining how our tool performs in these areas relative to established tools, we aim to demonstrate its unique contributions, particularly in the context of gender analysis in historical research.

Furthermore, this comparative analysis will not only highlight the advances introduced by this research but also identify potential areas for improvement. By critically evaluating our tool against others in the field, we ensure that it meets the highest standards of accuracy, clarity, and methodological rigour. This process is crucial for validating the effectiveness of our tool for historians and gender studies scholars.

Finally, case studies will provide a robust framework for evaluating our tool, ensuring that its design and functionalities contribute meaningfully to the study of gendered networks in historical chronicles.

4.4 Conclusion and Summary

In this chapter, we have detailed the methodology used in this study to visualise historical chronicle networks. We discussed how networks are defined and visualised, the centrality measures used to identify key nodes, the algorithms employed for community detection, and the specific choices made in terms of node shapes, colours, and edge styles to represent gender and relationships within the network.

The methodologies outlined in this chapter provide a comprehensive framework for analyzing the complex relationships and dynamics captured in historical chronicles. Using advanced network visualisation techniques and thoughtful design choices, this study seeks to uncover and highlight the often overlooked roles and representations of women in historical records. The use of two different tool models further enhances the robustness of the analysis, allowing for a deeper and more versatile exploration of the data.

As we move forward in the study, the findings generated through these methodologies will be critically analyzed and interpreted, shedding new light on the gender dynamics of historical chronicles and contributing to a more inclusive understanding of history. The next chapter will present the results of this analysis, exploring the implications of the findings and discussing how they align with or challenge existing historical narratives.

Chapter 5

Results and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, we extend the methodological framework established in the previous chapter by critically evaluating a range of network visualisation tools designed for the analysis of historical networks. The primary focus of this chapter is the application of the Genchron: Network Visualizer—a specialized tool developed for our research to address specific challenges in visualizing and analyzing complex social networks within historical contexts, particularly those involving gender dynamics in chronicle networks.

The development of Genchron was motivated by the need to overcome the limitations of existing visualisation tools, which often lack the interactivity, flexibility, and analytical depth required for the nuanced exploration of gendered networks within historical narratives. To provide a comprehensive evaluation, this chapter will also review and compare Genchron with other significant tools that have been instrumental in the field of HSNA. The analysis will include exploring tools discussed in Chapter 2 such as VAIroma, HisVA, PK-Clustering, ComBiNet, and methodologies from notable studies such as those by Pádraig MacCarron 2014 and Yose et al. 2018.

The objective of this chapter is multifaceted. First, it seeks to demonstrate how these tools facilitate the exploration of gendered networks in historical chronicles, providing historians with insights into the social structures and relationships that shaped historical events. Through the lens of these tools, the chapter will highlight the specific advantages that Genchron offers in this context, particularly in terms of gender representation, interactivity, user customisation, and real-time analytical capabilities.

Second, the chapter aims to critically evaluate how Genchron compares to other established tools in terms of usability, analytical depth, and effectiveness in visualizing gendered networks. This comparative analysis will assess the strengths and limitations of each tool, with a particular emphasis on how they address the unique challenges posed by historical data, such as incomplete records, bias, and the complexity of social relationships.

Third, the chapter will address the research gaps identified in Chapter 1, specifically

the need for tools that can more effectively highlight gender dynamics within historical networks. By exploring the capabilities of Genchron alongside other tools, the chapter will demonstrate how this new visualisation tool advances our understanding of gendered interactions in historical contexts, providing a more comprehensive and nuanced view of these networks.

Finally, the chapter will provide an in-depth analysis of the results obtained from using Genchron to visualize gendered networks, with a particular focus on the insights gained into the roles and relationships of female figures within these networks. This analysis will be accompanied by a discussion of how the findings contribute to the broader research questions posed in this thesis. The chapter will conclude with a reflection on the implications of these findings for future research in the field of digital humanities, particularly in the study of historical gendered networks.

5.2 Genchron: Network Visualizer

The *Genchron: Network Visualizer* represents a significant advancement in the field of Historical HSNA, particularly in the study of gendered networks within historical chronicles. This tool is developed using React JavaScript and Cytoscape.js. Genchron is specifically designed to address the limitations of existing network visualisation tools which often struggle to effectively handle the complexities and nuances inherent in historical data. The decision to use the React.js JavaScript framework ensures a highly responsive and interactive user interface Lazuardy, and Anggraini 2022 Byers 2023. Further, Cytoscape.js—a robust open-source graph visualisation library—enables the rendering and manipulation of large-scale networks with impressive efficiency and clarity Cytoscape.org 2024.

The development of Genchron was driven by the recognition that traditional network visualisation tools, such as Gephi and Pajek, though powerful, often lack the real-time interactivity and flexibility necessary for deep historical analysis Sapountzi, and Psannis 2018. These tools tend to be more static, requiring users to pre-define many aspects of the network before visualising it, which can limit the exploratory nature of historical research. Additionally, these tools also require familiarity and expertise in the code base and interface controls needed for running them Reina et al. 2020. This familiarity or expertise results in niche end users who spend considerable time learning and adapting to these tools. In contrast, Genchron is built to provide a dynamic environment where any users, irrespective of their area of expertise, can interact with the data continuously, allowing them to manipulate and customize visualisations in real time. This feature is crucial for historical research, where new insights can emerge at any point during the analysis, requiring a flexible tool that can adapt to evolving research questions and hypotheses.

5.2.1 Features and Functionalities

Genchron is equipped with a range of sophisticated features designed to enhance both the user experience and the analytical depth of historical network studies. These features include dynamic visualisation, multiple layout options, interactive filtering, centrality measures, and community detection. Each of these functionalities plays a critical role in enabling researchers to explore and interpret complex historical networks more effectively.

Dynamic Visualisation: One of the standout features of Genchron is its ability to dynamically visualise. Traditional tools where visualisations are often static and require substantial reconfiguration for any changes. Genchron allows users to adjust visual elements in real-time. This includes manipulating node size, colour, and opacity to emphasise specific network aspects such as key individuals, gender distinctions, or central figures based on their influence within the network. This real-time manipulation is particularly useful when testing different hypotheses or exploring various scenarios within gendered networks. For instance, by adjusting node sizes to reflect centrality measures, researchers can immediately identify the most influential figures within a network and explore how their relationships impacted historical events. This capability not only enhances the depth of the analysis but also facilitates a more nuanced understanding of the complex interactions that shape historical narratives.

Multiple Layout Options: Genchron offers multiple layout algorithms that provide different perspectives on the network's structure, each revealing unique aspects of the relationships and hierarchies within the data. The supported layouts include force-directed (FCoSE), circular (CiSE), and compound spring-embedded (CoSE), radial trees. The implementation of these layouts has been thoroughly discussed in Chapter 3. The FCoSE layout is particularly effective for uncovering hidden clusters and sub-groups within the network, which can be pivotal in understanding social structures. The CiSE layout, with its ability to organise nodes in circular clusters, is useful for visualising hierarchical relationships and for identifying the central nodes that connect different groups. The flexibility to switch between these layouts allows researchers to explore the same data from multiple angles, thus gaining a more comprehensive understanding of the network's dynamics.

Interactive Filtering: Genchron's interactive filtering capabilities are one of its most powerful features, enabling users to isolate and focus on specific sub-networks based on various attributes such as gender, named status, and relationship type. This is particularly useful in the analysis of gendered networks, where researchers may wish to examine the interactions involving only female figures or unnamed groups within a historical context. By allowing researchers to filter out irrelevant data and focus on the aspects most relevant to their research questions, Genchron makes it easier to perform detailed analyses of subnets as shown in Figure 5.1. For example, in a study of medieval religious communities, a researcher could use filtering options to isolate the interactions of female saints, thus gaining insight into their roles and influence within the broader religious network.

Centrality Measures: Centrality measures are critical in understanding the im-

Figure 5.1: Subnets explored using CoSE layout for *Eusebius-Jerome* data in Genchron

portance and influence of specific nodes within a network. Genchron incorporates advanced centrality measures such as betweenness centrality, closeness centrality, and degree centrality, providing researchers with the tools needed to quantify the significance of individual nodes. Figure 5.2 shows how centrality is also used as an overlay to streamline the analysis process by tracing important nodes. Further, the node properties UI also displays information related to other centrality measures when a particular node is selected as shown in Figure 5.3. Betweenness centrality, for instance, is particularly valuable in identifying key intermediaries who play a pivotal role in connecting different parts of the network. Closeness centrality helps to understand how quickly a node can access all other nodes in the network, indicating the potential for influence. Degree centrality, on the other hand, reflects the number of direct connections a node has, highlighting the most connected individuals or groups. These metrics are essential for analyzing the roles of gendered actors within historical networks, offering quantitative insights into their relative importance and influence. For example, in examining a medieval political network, nodes with high betweenness centrality might represent power brokers¹ whose decisions had far-reaching impacts between different communities or factions.

Community Detection: Another significant feature of Genchron is its community detection algorithms, which are indispensable for identifying clusters or communities within a network. These algorithms help uncover the social structures and affiliations

¹Betweenness centrality has often been used analogously with the term power brokers in socio-political complex networks. They represent influential connectors within the networks Hafner-Burton, and Montgomery 2010.

Figure 5.2: Filtered networks of *Cassiodorus* in case layout (left) and *Prosper* in radial force directed (right) with their centrality filter overlay in Genchron

Figure 5.3: *Shelah*, Son of Judah node selected, with neighbouring connections highlighted and node properties displayed in sidebar UI with centrality overlay on in Genchron.

that played crucial roles in shaping historical events. For example, community detection can reveal how certain religious sects or political factions were interconnected and how these connections influenced broader societal dynamics. Figure 5.4 explores community structures in networks of three important data sources *Isidore*, *Whitelock* and *Bede*. By analyzing these communities, researchers can gain insights into the social fabric of historical periods, understanding how different groups interacted and how these interactions contributed to historical developments. For example, in the context of gendered network analysis, community detection might reveal the existence of female-centric communities that were previously overlooked in traditional historical narratives, thereby providing a more nuanced understanding of women's roles in history.

Figure 5.4: Community structures in Cise layout for filtered *Isidore* (left) *Whitelock* (middle) and *Bede* (right) networks in Genchron

5.2.2 Usability and User Experience (UX)

The design of Genchron places a strong emphasis on user-friendliness and accessibility, ensuring that the tool can be effectively utilized by both novice and experienced researchers irrespective of their field of study. The intuitive control panel, located on the left side of the interface, allows users to quickly and easily adjust various visualisation parameters, such as node size, colour, and layout type. This design choice aims to reduce the learning curve for new users, allowing them to focus on their analytical tasks rather than grappling with the tool's functionality.

Visual Feedback:

One of the most valuable features of Genchron is its ability to provide immediate visual feedback as users adjust the network parameters. This feature is critical for the analytical process, as it allows researchers to see the effects of different configurations instantaneously, refining their interpretations and hypotheses as they go. For example, by adjusting the size of the node based on centrality measures, users can quickly identify the most influential figures within a network, facilitating a deeper understanding of the social dynamics at play. This immediate feedback loop is crucial for historians who need to make sense of complex, multi-faceted data, enabling them to iterate on their analyses more effectively.

Figure 5.5: Genchron UI with *Eusebius-Jerome* dataset loaded in Radial Tree layout; The node *Helen of Troy* selected showing her neighbouring nodes *Castor*, *Pollux* and *Theseus* selected.

visualisation Standpoint:

From a visualisation standpoint, Genchron excels in managing large and complex networks without sacrificing clarity and readability. This is evident in Figure 5.5 which shows the Genchron UI with the Eusebius-Jerome dataset. This dataset is quite large compared to other datasets we have worked with as evident in Table 3.1. The use of colour-coding, edge bundling, and node size adjustments based on centrality measures helps to reduce visual clutter, making the network structure more interpretable. This is particularly important when dealing with historical networks, where the sheer volume of data can often lead to overwhelming and incomprehensible visualisations. Additionally,

Genchron's ability to switch between different layouts provides multiple perspectives on the same network, helping to uncover hidden patterns and relationships that might be missed with a single static layout. This capability is especially valuable in historical research, where the ability to view the same data from different angles can lead to new insights and a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of the network.

5.2.3 Methodological Integration

The integration of Genchron within the methodological framework of HSNA is both seamless and innovative, aligning closely with the approaches discussed in Chapter 3. Genchron is designed with the specific needs of HSNA in mind, offering tools and functionalities that support the detailed exploration of gendered interactions within historical texts. The tool's real-time interaction capabilities are particularly well-suited to the iterative nature of HSNA, where researchers often need to refine their analyses based on new insights or evolving research questions.

HSNA requires a dynamic and flexible approach to data analysis, as the exploration of historical networks often reveals new questions and hypotheses that necessitate further investigation. Genchron supports this iterative process by allowing researchers to continuously interact with and manipulate the network data, testing different configurations and filters in real time. This capability is essential for historians who need to adapt their analyses as new patterns emerge, ensuring that the research remains responsive to the complexities of the data.

Genchron's design demonstrates a keen grasp of the specific difficulties associated with gendered network analysis in historical settings. Conventional tools often fall short of capturing the detailed and complex nature of gendered relationships, especially in situations where women's contributions have been underrepresented or hidden in historical records. Genchron tackles these issues by offering sophisticated filtering and visualisation capabilities that enable researchers to selectively examine and dissect gendered interactions with enhanced accuracy. For example, by narrowing the network to focus solely on female figures, researchers can dive into the roles and impact of women within historical networks in a manner that is both thorough and enlightening.

Finally, Genchron's development was guided by the broader research objectives outlined in Chapter 1, particularly the goal of creating tools that can more effectively highlight gender dynamics within historical networks. By offering a platform that combines advanced analytical capabilities with a user-friendly interface, Genchron enables researchers to explore historical data in new and innovative ways, shedding light on the complex and often overlooked roles of gender in shaping historical events. This aligns with the thesis's overarching goal of advancing the field of digital humanities by providing tools that support more nuanced and comprehensive analyses of historical texts.

Genchron represents a significant step forward in the field of Historical Social Network Analysis, offering a powerful and flexible tool that addresses many of the limitations of existing visualisation platforms. By combining real-time interactivity with advanced

analytical capabilities, Genchron enables researchers to explore historical networks with unprecedented depth and precision, particularly in the analysis of gendered interactions. As the following sections will demonstrate, Genchron's contributions to the study of historical networks are both profound and far-reaching, offering new insights and perspectives on the complex social dynamics that have shaped our understanding of history.

5.3 Comparative Analysis of Visualisation Tools

In this section, we conduct a comparative analysis of various network visualisation tools that have been instrumental in Historical Social Network Analysis (HSNA), focusing on their capabilities in contextualizing historical data, handling network complexity, and providing methodological insights into gendered networks. Specifically, we will examine VAIroma, HisVA, PK-Clustering, and ComBiNet, as well as methodologies from Yose et al. 2018 and Pádraig MacCarron 2014. Table 5.1 shows the summarised comparative analysis of the tools addressed in this section. The analysis will emphasize how Genchron addresses the limitations of these tools and fills the research gaps identified in Chapter 1 of this thesis.

5.3.1 VAIroma and HisVA: Historical Contextualization

VAIroma: VAIroma is a visual analytics system specifically designed for the exploration of Roman history through the integration of textual and visual data. The system offers multiple views, including timeline, geographic, and topic views, which allow users to examine the relationships between places, events, and figures within the Roman historical context Cho et al. 2015. The strength of VAIroma lies in its ability to provide a structured and guided analysis, making it easier for researchers to contextualize historical events and understand the interplay of various factors over time. For example, the timeline view in VAIroma effectively shows how certain events are temporally related, while the geographic view maps these events onto specific locations, offering a spatial perspective on historical narratives.

However, VAIroma's utility is somewhat limited by its focus on predefined datasets. The tool is tailored for Roman history and is not easily adaptable to other historical contexts or datasets. This limitation restricts its applicability, particularly in research areas outside its intended scope. Moreover, VAIroma lacks the flexibility that is crucial for exploratory data analysis, as it does not allow users to manipulate the data or visualisations in real time. This static nature can be a significant drawback when researchers need to explore multiple hypotheses or dynamically adjust their focus during the analysis.

While VAIroma excels in providing a comprehensive and guided analysis of Roman history, it does not afford the same level of interactivity or user-driven exploration as Genchron. The static nature of VAIroma's visualisations starkly contrasts with Genchron's dynamic capabilities, which permit researchers to customize their analyses

in real-time. For instance, Genchron enables users to adjust node sizes, colours, and layouts instantaneously, facilitating the exploration of various aspects of the network from diverse perspectives. This flexibility is particularly invaluable in the context of HSNA, where researchers often need to pivot between different views and analytical approaches as new insights are garnered. Moreover, whereas VAIroma is confined to a specific historical context, Genchron's design permits its application across a broad spectrum of historical datasets, rendering it a more versatile tool for historical research.

HisVA: HisVA builds upon the capabilities of VAIroma by incorporating geospatial analysis, thereby enabling researchers to study historical narratives within their geographical contexts Han et al. 2021. HisVA is particularly effective in visualizing the relationships between historical figures, events, and locations over time, offering a multi-dimensional view of history that integrates both temporal and spatial data. For instance, HisVA can map the movements of historical figures across different regions, providing insights into how geographical factors influenced their interactions and decisions.

Like VAIroma, HisVA is tailored for data with a strong geographical component and lacks the broader applicability and advanced analytical features of Genchron, such as centrality measures and community detection. This makes HisVA less effective for complex networks without significant spatial elements or for social, rather than geographical, relationships in historical texts. While HisVA excels in geospatial analysis, it cannot handle broader historical network complexities. Genchron is adaptable to various networks, including non-geographical ones. In gendered networks focusing on social interactions, Genchron's centrality measures and community detection algorithms provide a comprehensive toolset. These features make Genchron versatile for exploring historical networks, especially those involving gender dynamics.

5.3.2 PK-Clustering and ComBiNet: Network Complexity

PK-Clustering: PK-Clustering is a specialized tool designed to address the challenges of clustering within historical networks, particularly those that feature overlapping or nested communities Pister, Buono, et al. 2020. The tool is highly effective in identifying significant subgroups within a network, such as political factions, religious sects, or other closely-knit communities. For example, in a study of medieval religious communities, PK clustering could be used to identify and analyse different monastic orders and their interactions within the broader ecclesiastical network.

PK-Clustering focusses on clustering in network analysis, but lacks the visual analytics of tools like Genchron. It excels at identifying specific communities but does not provide tools for broader network analysis, limiting its use for comprehensive historical network research. Genchron, however, integrates clustering with centrality measures and dynamic filtering, allowing for a holistic approach. For example, after identifying a cluster of influential women in a medieval network, researchers can use Genchron's centrality measures to understand their roles and influence within the larger network.

Tool	Strengths	Weaknesses	Genchron
VAiRoma	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strong in Roman historical analysis - Multiple views (time-line, geographic) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited to Roman history - Static, no real-time adjustments 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genchron offers dynamic, real-time visualisations - Applicable to various historical contexts
HisVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrates geospatial analysis - Temporal and spatial views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focused on geographic data - Lacks advanced analytics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genchron supports non-geographic networks - Offers advanced tools for social interaction analysis
PK-Clustering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Effective at identifying network clusters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Focused only on clustering 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genchron integrates clustering with broader analysis tools
ComBiNet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Handles complex, multilayered networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complex, requires expertise - Less interactive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genchron balances power with ease of use - More accessible for non-specialists
Yose et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reveals hidden structures in historical texts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Static, predefined analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genchron allows dynamic exploration and hypothesis testing
MacCarron et al. (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlights marginalized groups in networks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Relies on static visualisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Genchron offers dynamic gendered network analysis - Provides deeper insights with advanced filtering

Table 5.1: Comparative Analysis of Network Visualisation Tools

ComBiNet: ComBiNet is a tool designed for the analysis of complex networks with multiple layers or types of relationships Pister, Prieur, and Fekete 2023. It is particularly useful in Historical Social Network Analysis, where researchers often need to consider various types of relationships simultaneously, such as political alliances, economic exchanges, and familial ties. ComBiNet excels in visualizing how these different relationships interact and evolve, providing a comprehensive view of the multifaceted nature of historical networks.

ComBiNet's complexity can hinder its optimal use, requiring high expertise and limiting accessibility for those without advanced network analysis skills. While excellent for multilayered network analysis, it lacks the interactivity and user-friendliness of Genchron. Despite ComBiNet's essential role in handling complex historical data, its sophisticated nature can be prohibitive. Genchron balances functionality and usability, making it suitable for various research contexts. Though it may not detail multilayered networks as comprehensively as ComBiNet, Genchron's intuitive interface and real-time features enable thorough network analysis without extensive technical knowledge. This usability is crucial in HSNA, where diverse researchers need robust, user-friendly tools.

5.3.3 Yose et al. (2018) and MacCarron (2014): Methodological Insights

Network analysis of *Cogadh Gaedhel re Gallaibh*:

Yose et al. 2018 applied network analysis to the Viking Age in Ireland, as depicted in the *Cogadh Gaedhel re Gallaibh*, a historical text detailing the conflicts between the Irish and the Vikings. Their study revealed intricate social and political relationships within the text, challenging traditional narratives and uncovering hidden structures that were not immediately apparent through conventional historical analysis. This work demonstrated the potential of network analysis to offer new insights into historical narratives by revealing connections and dynamics that might otherwise be overlooked.

The approach used by Yose et al. 2018 serves as a foundational example of how network analysis can transform our understanding of historical texts. However, their methodology was largely static, requiring predefined network structures and relationships. Genchron enhances this approach by allowing researchers to dynamically test and refine their hypotheses through real-time interaction with the data. This capability is crucial for uncovering complex dynamics that may not be immediately apparent in a static analysis. For instance, in analyzing the complex network within the *Cogadh Gaedhel re Gallaibh*, a researcher could use Genchron to iteratively explore different configurations of the network, adjusting filters and centrality measures to reveal how gendered roles and relationships evolved. This dynamic approach provides a more detailed and nuanced interpretation of gendered networks, making it easier to identify key figures and relationships that played significant roles in the historical narrative.

Network analysis by MacCarron:

Pádraig MacCarron 2014 employed network analysis to study medieval hagiographies, with a particular focus on exploring the roles of women within these narratives. Their research demonstrated how network visualisation could challenge traditional interpretations and highlight the contributions of marginalised groups, particularly women, who are often under-represented in mythological texts. By visualising the networks of interactions between saints, clerics, and other figures, they were able to identify patterns of influence and power that had previously gone unnoticed.

Genchron builds upon the methodologies utilized by Pádraig MacCarron 2014, offering tools specifically engineered for the examination of gendered networks. Its sophisticated filtering and visualisation capabilities facilitate a more nuanced analysis of gender dynamics within historical texts, elucidating patterns and relationships that may elude less interactive tools. For instance, while MacCarron's study centred on static visualisations to delineate the roles of women within medieval networks, Genchron enables a more dynamic interrogation of these roles. Scholars can manipulate the network in real-time, applying various filters to examine how gender, social status, and religious affiliation interlinked to shape the lives and legacies of historical figures. Moreover, the incorporation of centrality measures and community detection in Genchron provides

additional analytical dimensions, assisting researchers in quantifying the influence of women within these networks and comparing their roles across different historical epochs. This feature is particularly invaluable for longitudinal studies, allowing researchers to monitor changes in gender dynamics over time.

5.3.4 Addressing the Research Gap

The development of Genchron directly addresses the research gaps identified in Chapter 1. Traditional tools, while effective for static analyses, do not provide the level of interactivity and user control necessary for fully exploring complex gendered networks. For example, tools like VAIroma and HisVA, while valuable for their specific applications, are limited by their static nature and predefined datasets as evident from the previous discussion. These limitations can hinder the exploration of new hypotheses or the examination of networks from different perspectives, which are essential for a comprehensive understanding of historical narratives.

Genchron's real-time manipulation and visualisation enhance research by tailoring analyses to specific questions, offering deeper insights into gender dynamics in historical narratives. Its flexible platform allows comprehensive exploration of historical networks, revealing new research opportunities. In medieval vitae, Genchron helps researchers examine women's roles from various angles with different centrality measures and filters, uncovering influence patterns traditional tools might miss. Its user-friendly interface makes it accessible to more researchers, even those new to network analysis. This accessibility advances digital humanities, fostering interdisciplinary collaboration to tackle complex questions. By balancing technical sophistication with ease of use, Genchron enables in-depth analyses of historical networks, especially gendered interactions.

In summary, Genchron marks a major advancement in Historical Social Network Analysis by overcoming the constraints of current tools and opening new avenues for investigating gender dynamics in historical contexts. Its real-time interaction, sophisticated analytical features, and ease of use make it an essential asset for historians, digital humanists, and other researchers exploring the intricate social relationships that have influenced our historical comprehension. As demonstrated in this chapter's analysis, Genchron not only improves our capacity to explore historical networks but also provides fresh insights and viewpoints that can question traditional narratives and enhance our grasp of the past.

5.4 Discussion of Research Questions

5.4.1 Design of Visual Analytics Tools

The development and subsequent refinement of Genchron have yielded profound insights into our RQ1 in Chapter 1. This involved studying the design of tools optimized

for elucidating gendered networks within historical contexts. Genchron's design philosophy, emphasizing interactivity, adaptability, and user-centred control, has proven instrumental in uncovering the complex dynamics of gender within historical networks. In contrast to traditional static tools, Genchron's architecture enables real-time interaction with data, permitting researchers to dynamically adjust visual parameters—such as node size, colour, and layout—to better capture the intricacies of gendered relationships and interactions.

Figure 5.6: Influential women nodes in *Marcellinus* dataset loaded in CoSE layout (right) and with degree layover (left); The nodes *Flaccilla (daughter of Arcadius)*, *Marina*, *Pulcheria*, *Matasuentha*, and *Honoria*

Integrating centrality metrics such as betweenness, closeness, and degree centrality within Genchron allows researchers to quantify the significance of nodes (representing individuals or entities) and elucidate their roles within broader social structures. This was particularly evident in the analyses of historical networks, where prominent female figures, often marginalized in traditional narratives, emerged as pivotal connectors or influencers within their communities. Figure 5.6 shows the network generated from the *Marcellinus* dataset representing influential women nodes in the network. Further, investigation of this network reveals that these female nodes have high betweenness evident from their connections to the nodes with the highest centralities as shown in Figure 5.7. These nodes are essentially acting as bridges in a dominantly male network.

The functionalities, enhanced by real-time interactivity, highlight Genchron's capacity to not only visualize but also analyze complex historical networks, offering a platform that is both methodologically rigorous and user-centric. The comparative analysis with other tools, such as VAIroma and HisVA, further accentuates the distinctiveness of Genchron's design. While these tools provide valuable insights within their

Figure 5.7: Influential women nodes in *Marcellinus Flaccilla* (daughter of *Arcadius*), *Marina*, *Pulcheria*, *Matasuentha*, and *Honorio* connections investigation

respective contexts—such as geospatial analysis or thematic exploration—they lack the comprehensive, user-driven approach that Genchron embodies. This study demonstrates that the design of visual analytics tools like Genchron, which integrate flexibility with advanced analytical capabilities, is crucial for effectively elucidating the gendered dimensions of historical networks. The ability to interact with these networks in real time not only enhances analytical depth but also opens new avenues for historical inquiry, allowing researchers to uncover the often-overlooked contributions of women and other marginalized groups within historical narratives.

5.4.2 Impact of Design Choices

The design choices embedded in Genchron have immensely influenced the way gendered data is interpreted within historical networks. By emphasizing real-time interaction and dynamic visualisation, Genchron has enabled researchers to explore multiple analytical perspectives and configurations of the network, revealing relational dynamics that might otherwise remain obscured addressing our RQ2. This capability is critical for understanding the exploration of how gender intersects with other social, political, and economic factors.

This visual differentiation facilitated a deeper understanding of the power dynamics at play, illustrating how certain women acted as central nodes within their communities, influencing both local and broader social structures as evident in the previous section in Figure 5.6. The community detection algorithms further enhanced this analysis by uncovering distinct sub-groups within the networks, offering a more detailed view of

the social structures that influenced historical events. This level of analytical granularity is difficult to achieve with static tools explored in the literature review in Chapter 2. This underscores the importance of Genchron's design in advancing our understanding of gendered networks.

Figure 5.8: Exploratory analysis of the node *Romans* in *Isidore* dataset using different layouts- radial tree(left) with degree layover, CoSE(middle) unfiltered, and Cise(right) with degree layover

Moreover, the design choices in Genchron have enabled a more exploratory approach to network analysis, where researchers can iteratively refine their hypotheses and interpretations. This iterative process is crucial for historical research, where the complexity of the data often requires multiple layers of analysis. For example, in the exploration of the connections of *Romans* node in *Isidore's* networks, researchers could experiment with different configurations to uncover hidden connections and patterns, thereby gaining new insights into the role of genders within these historical narratives as shown in Figure 5.8.

The ability to visualize and analyze these networks in real time has also contributed to a more accurate interpretation of the data. By providing immediate visual feedback, Genchron allows researchers to quickly assess the impact of their analytical choices and make adjustments as needed. This iterative process not only enhances the accuracy of the analysis but also fosters a more engaging and interactive research experience, where the researcher is an active participant in the discovery process.

5.5 Challenges and Limitations

To address our third research question RQ3 we need to acknowledge certain challenges Genchron presents. One of the primary limitations is the quality and completeness of the historical data, which can significantly affect the accuracy and reliability of the visualisations. Historical data is often incomplete, fragmented, or biased, which can lead to misleading interpretations, particularly when analyzing complex networks with many interrelated components. This issue was evident in the analysis of the *Isidore* and *Whitelock* networks, where gaps in the data sometimes made it difficult to draw definitive conclusions about the roles and relationships of certain individuals.

Another challenge is the demand that Genchron's real-time interaction capabilities place on system resources, especially when dealing with very large datasets. While the tool is designed to handle large-scale networks, its performance can be constrained by the limitations of the hardware it is running on. This was particularly noticeable in the analysis of networks from *Eusebius-Jerome* networks, where the size and complexity of the data sometimes led to slower processing times and reduced responsiveness. Future work should focus on enhancing Genchron's data preprocessing capabilities and optimizing its performance to ensure that it can handle even larger and more complex networks efficiently.

The algorithms used in Genchron, while sophisticated, are not free from bias. These biases can be introduced at various stages of the data processing and visualisation pipeline, from the initial data input to the final visual output. For instance, the choice of centrality measures, community detection algorithms, or even the visual representation of nodes and edges can all influence the perceived importance of different entities within the network. If not carefully managed, these biases can reinforce existing stereotypes or misconceptions, rather than challenging them as intended.

In addition to these technical challenges, there is also the issue of interpreting the visualisations produced by Genchron. While the tool provides a wealth of information through its dynamic visualisations, interpreting this data requires a high level of expertise. Researchers must be careful not to oversimplify or misinterpret the visualisations, particularly when dealing with complex historical data. Given the complexities involved in both the data and the tools used to analyze it, interdisciplinary collaboration is crucial. The development and effective use of tools like Genchron require the combined expertise of historians, data scientists, and visual analysts. Historians provide the necessary contextual understanding and help ensure that the data is interpreted correctly. Data scientists contribute their expertise in algorithm design and data processing, while visual analysts ensure that the visual outputs are both informative and accessible. However, fostering such collaboration is itself a challenge. It requires effective communication between disciplines that may have different terminologies, methodologies, and priorities. Ensuring that all members of the team have a shared understanding of the project's goals and constraints is essential for the successful integration of their diverse skills and perspectives.

5.6 Conclusion

This chapter has demonstrated the substantial advancements that interactive network visualisation tools like Genchron bring to the study of historically gendered networks. By enabling a deeper, more nuanced exploration of data, these tools not only broaden our understanding of historical narratives but also pave the way for future research in digital humanities and beyond. The ability to interact with data in real time, apply dynamic filters, and visualize complex network structures has opened new avenues for academic inquiry, providing a powerful platform for uncovering the hidden dynamics of gendered interactions within historical texts.

As this study has shown, Genchron represents a significant step forward in the field of Historical Social Network Analysis (HSNA). Its versatile and user-friendly design makes it an effective tool for exploring the rich and complex relationships that shape our understanding of history. By addressing the research gaps identified in Chapter 1, Genchron has proven to be a valuable addition to the existing array of network visualisation tools, offering new insights into the roles of gender within historical networks and challenging traditional narratives that may have overlooked the contributions of marginalized groups.

In summary, Genchron has not only enhanced our ability to analyze historical networks but has also highlighted the importance of gender as a critical dimension in historical research. By providing a platform that allows researchers to explore these dynamics in real time, Genchron has opened new avenues for historical research and analysis, offering a powerful tool for uncovering the hidden dynamics of gendered interactions within historical texts. As the field of digital humanities continues to evolve, tools like Genchron will play an increasingly important role in shaping our understanding of history and the social structures that have influenced it. The advancements demonstrated in this chapter are not just technological but also methodological, pushing the boundaries of what is possible in the study of historical networks and offering new possibilities for research that is more inclusive, comprehensive, and insightful.

By integrating advanced features such as dynamic visualisation, centrality measures, and community detection, Genchron sets a new standard for what network visualisation tools can achieve in historical research. It bridges the gap between static historical analysis and the dynamic, interactive exploration that is necessary to fully understand the complexities of past societies. In doing so, Genchron not only provides a more accurate representation of historical gendered networks but also challenges us to reconsider how we approach the study of history in the digital age.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

6.1 Summary

This thesis embarked on a comprehensive exploration of visual analytics tools designed to highlight gendered networks within historical chronicles, with a particular focus on the late antique and early medieval periods. The motivation driving this research was the recognition that traditional historical methodologies have often marginalized or entirely overlooked the contributions of women, leading to a skewed understanding of historical social structures. By leveraging the capabilities of visual analytics, this study aimed to uncover the complexities of gender dynamics and provide a more nuanced and accurate representation of history. The research was guided by three primary research questions:

RQ1: How can visual analytics tools be designed to effectively highlight gendered networks within historical chronicles?

RQ2: How do design choices in these tools impact the interpretation of gendered data?

RQ3: What are the challenges and limitations encountered in using visual analytics tools for analyzing gendered networks?

To answer these questions, this thesis involved the design, development and iterative refinement of Genchron, a novel visual analytics tool specifically tailored for the exploration of gendered networks in historical data. The research also included a comparative analysis of Genchron with other existing tools and methodologies to evaluate its effectiveness and to understand the broader implications of using visual analytics in historical research.

The study demonstrated that visual analytics tools like Genchron, with their emphasis on interactivity, flexibility, and user control, are essential for uncovering the complex dynamics of gender within historical networks. These tools provide a platform that allows researchers to engage with historical data in real time, offering new perspectives and deeper insights into the roles and relationships that have historically shaped social structures.

The impact of design choices on the interpretation of gendered networks was also thoroughly examined. The ability to adjust various visual parameters, such as node sizes, colours, and layout configurations, was shown to be crucial in highlighting the often subtle roles of women within these networks. Moreover, the integration of analytical tools like centrality measures and community detection algorithms within Genchron enabled a more detailed exploration of social hierarchies and power dynamics that have traditionally been obscured in historical narratives.

However, the research also identified significant challenges and limitations in using visual analytics tools for this purpose. Issues related to data quality and completeness were found to be particularly problematic, as historical data often suffers from gaps, biases, and inaccuracies that can lead to misleading visualisations. Additionally, the technical demands of real-time interaction with large datasets presented challenges in terms of system performance and usability. The potential for misinterpretation of visualisations was also highlighted as a critical concern, emphasizing the need for interdisciplinary collaboration to ensure that these tools are both accurate and meaningful.

6.2 Discussion and Contribution

The contributions of this study are significant, particularly within the realms of Historical Social Network Analysis (HSNA) and digital humanities. The findings address the core objectives of RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3, providing a comprehensive understanding of how visual analytics tools can be designed, implemented, and utilised to explore gendered networks in historical data.

This research has demonstrated that the design of visual analytics tools like Genchron plays a pivotal role in effectively highlighting gendered networks within historical chronicles. The emphasis on interactivity, flexibility, and user control within Genchron allowed researchers to explore historical data from multiple analytical perspectives, revealing hidden dynamics and previously overlooked contributions of women. The ability to customise visual elements, such as node sizes and colours, based on centrality measures was particularly impactful, enabling a more nuanced understanding of the roles and relationships within these networks.

The study also showed that the integration of community detection algorithms and centrality measures within these tools provides a deeper level of analysis. These features allowed for the identification of key individuals and subgroups within the networks, offering insights into the social structures and power dynamics that influenced historical events. By applying these methods to historical texts, the research contributed to a more inclusive and accurate portrayal of history, challenging traditional narratives that have often marginalised the contributions of women.

The design choices made in the development of Genchron were found to have a profound impact on the interpretation of gendered data. The real-time interaction capabilities of the tool allowed researchers to experiment with different analytical perspectives, making it possible to uncover layers of relational dynamics that might otherwise remain hidden. For example, the ability to adjust node sizes and colours based on

centrality measures helped to highlight key players within the network, providing new insights into their roles and relationships. Additionally, the tool's community detection algorithms revealed the existence of distinct sub-groups within the networks, offering a more detailed understanding of the social structures that influenced historical events.

Moreover, the visualisations produced by Genchron facilitated a more intuitive and immediate understanding of complex historical networks. The ability to dynamically explore the data, combined with the tool's user-friendly interface, made it easier for researchers to engage with the data and interpret the findings accurately. This highlights the importance of thoughtful design in the development of visual analytics tools, as these choices directly influence the quality and depth of the insights that can be derived from the data.

The research also brought to light several challenges and limitations associated with using visual analytics tools for analyzing gendered networks. One of the primary challenges identified was the quality and completeness of historical data. Incomplete or biased data can lead to misleading visualisations, which in turn can result in inaccurate interpretations. This is a significant concern in historical research, where the data is often fragmented and subject to various forms of bias. The study underscored the need for rigorous data preprocessing and validation processes to mitigate these issues and ensure the reliability of the visualisations produced.

Another challenge was the technical demands of real-time interaction with large datasets. Although Genchron's real-time interaction capabilities were found to be powerful and essential for exploratory analysis, they also placed significant demands on system resources. This can limit the effectiveness of the tool when analysing extremely large or complex networks, where performance issues may hinder the usability of the tool. The research highlighted the need for ongoing optimisation of these tools to improve their performance and scalability, particularly as historical datasets continue to grow in size and complexity.

The potential for misinterpretation of visualisations was also identified as a critical challenge. The study emphasized the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration between historians, computer scientists, and graphic designers to develop tools that are both user-friendly and methodologically rigorous. By working together, these experts can ensure that the visualisations produced are accurate and meaningful, minimizing the risk of oversimplification or misinterpretation.

In addition to these contributions, this study also provided practical guidelines for designing visual analytics tools that are sensitive to the nuances of gender representation. The methodologies developed in this research can be applied to other historical periods and datasets, offering a framework for uncovering the hidden dynamics of gendered interactions in various historical contexts.

6.3 Future Direction and Implications

The findings of this study open several promising avenues for future research and development, particularly in response to the challenges and limitations identified in

RQ3.

One of the key areas for future research is the enhancement of data preprocessing capabilities within visual analytics tools like Genchron. Improving the accuracy and completeness of historical data is crucial for ensuring the reliability of the visualisations produced. This includes developing advanced methods for dealing with incomplete or biased data, as well as refining the algorithms used for community detection and centrality calculations. Future work could focus on integrating machine learning techniques to automate the identification and correction of data biases, thereby improving the overall quality of the data.

As historical datasets continue to grow in size and complexity, there is an increasing need for tools that can handle these challenges without compromising performance or usability. Future research should focus on optimising the performance of visual analytics tools like Genchron, particularly for analysing larger and more complex networks. This may involve the development of new algorithms that are more efficient and scalable, or the integration of parallel processing techniques to enhance the tool's ability to handle large datasets in real-time.

Another important area for future research is improving the interpretation of visualisations produced by tools like Genchron. Although the tools developed in this study have provided valuable information on gendered networks, the risk of oversimplification or misinterpretation remains. Future work should focus on developing more intuitive and user-friendly interfaces that guide researchers in accurately interpreting the visualisations. This might include the integration of tutorial systems that provide step-by-step guidance on how to use the tools effectively, or the development of best practices for interpreting the visualisations within the context of historical research.

Expanding the Application of Methodologies The implications of this research extend beyond the specific historical periods and datasets studied here. The methodologies developed in this thesis have the potential to be applied to a wide range of historical contexts, providing new insights into the roles of marginalised groups in history. Future research could explore the application of these methodologies to different historical periods, cultures, and datasets, expanding our understanding of how gender dynamics have shaped social structures in time and space.

The challenges identified in this study highlight the importance of interdisciplinary collaboration in the development of visual analytics tools. Future research should continue to foster collaboration between historians, computer scientists, graphic designers, and other experts to ensure that the tools developed are both accurate and user-friendly. By working together, these experts can develop tools that not only provide valuable insights into historical networks but also help to advance the broader field of digital humanities.

In conclusion, this study has demonstrated the power of visual analytics tools in uncovering the hidden dynamics of gendered networks within historical texts. By challenging traditional narratives and providing new insight into the roles of women in history, this research has made a significant contribution to the fields of Historical Social Network Analysis (HSNA) and digital humanities. The findings from this study will serve

as a foundation for future research and development in this area, paving the way for more inclusive and accurate portrayals of history in the years to come. As the field of digital humanities continues to evolve, tools like Genchron will play an increasingly important role in shaping our understanding of history and the social structures that have influenced it, offering new perspectives on the complex and often overlooked dynamics of gendered interactions in historical contexts.

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Appendix A: Data Preprocessing

Algorithm 5 Preprocessing Algorithm for Network visualisation

- 1: **Input:** CSV file with historical data
 - 2: **Output:** Cleaned and structured data for network visualisation
 - 3: **procedure** PREPROCESSDATA
 - 4: **Step 1: Data Loading**
 - 5: Load the CSV file using `Papa.parse`
 - 6: Store the parsed data in a structured format
 - 7: **Step 2: Data Cleaning and Normalization**
 - 8: **for** each row in data **do**
 - 9: Trim whitespace from keys and values
 - 10: Normalize the gender value to a valid set {M, F, X, V, U}
 - 11: **if** gender value is invalid or missing **then**
 - 12: Set gender to 'U' (Unknown)
 - 13: **end if**
 - 14: **end for**
 - 15: Group columns with similar or redundant data
 - 16: Filter out irrelevant rows, such as age labels (FIRST AGE, SECOND AGE, etc.)
 - 17: **end procedure**
-

```
1 const cleanData = (data) => {
2   const sjoin = (x) => x.filter(Boolean).join("/");
3
4   data = data.map(row => {
5     const cleanedRow = {};
6     Object.keys(row).forEach(key => {
7       const trimmedKey = key.trim();
8       cleanedRow[trimmedKey] = row[key].trim();
9     });
10
11     const validGenders = ['M', 'F', 'X', 'V', 'U'];
12     cleanedRow['Gender'] = (cleanedRow['Gender'] || 'U').toUpperCase();
```

```
13     if (!validGenders.includes(cleanedRow['Gender'])) {
14         console.warn('Unexpected gender value: ${cleanedRow['Gender']} for
15         entity ${cleanedRow['Name']}');
16         cleanedRow['Gender'] = 'U';
17     }
18     return cleanedRow;
19 });
20
21 const columns = Object.keys(data[0]);
22 const groupedData = columns.reduce((acc, col) => {
23     acc[col] = data.map(row => row[col]).filter(Boolean);
24     return acc;
25 }, {});
26
27 for (const key in grouped data) {
28     groupedData[key] = sjoin(groupedData[key]);
29 }
30
31 const irrelevantNames = ['FIRST AGE', 'SECOND AGE', 'THIRD AGE', 'FOURTH
32     AGE', 'FIFTH AGE', 'SIXTH AGE'];
33 data = data.filter(row => !irrelevantNames.includes(row['Name'].
34     toUpperCase()));
35 }
```

Listing 6.1: JavaScript code for Preprocessing

Appendix B: Network Creation

```
1 // Node and Edge Creation
2 const processCSVData = (data) => {
3   const nodes = new Set();
4   const edges = [];
5   const nodeIds = new Set();
6
7   data.forEach((row) => {
8     const sourceNode = (row.Name || 'Unknown').trim();
9
10    if (Object.keys(row).every(key => key === 'Name' || row[key].trim()
11    === '')) {
12      console.warn('Skipping row with only name: ${sourceNode}');
13      return;
14    }
15
16    const gender = row.Gender.trim().toUpperCase();
17    const validGenders = ['M', 'F', 'X', 'V', 'U'];
18    if (!validGenders.includes(gender)) {
19      console.warn('Unexpected gender value: ${gender} for entity ${
20      sourceNode}');
21    }
22
23    const named = (row['Named/Unnamed'] || 'Unnamed').trim();
24    const lifestage = (row['Life cycle'] || 'Unknown').trim();
25    const group = (row.Groups || 'General').trim();
26
27    if (!nodeIds.has(sourceNode)) {
28      nodes.add({
29        data: {
30          id: sourceNode,
31          gender: gender,
32          named: named,
33          group: group,
34          lifestage: lifestage,
35          genderColor: getNodeColor(gender),
36          shape: getNodeShape(gender),
37        },
38      },
```

```
36     group: 'nodes'
37   });
38   nodeIds.add(sourceNode);
39 }
40
41 const connections = ['Positive connections', 'Negative connections', '
Neutral', 'Post mortem/supernatural']
42   .map(key => row[key])
43   .filter(Boolean)
44   .flat();
45
46 connections.forEach((connection) => {
47   if (connection && !nodeIds.has(connection.trim())) {
48     nodes.add({
49       data: {
50         id: connection.trim(),
51         gender: gender,
52         named: named,
53         group: group,
54         lifestage: lifestage,
55         genderColor: getNodeColor(gender),
56         shape: getNodeShape(gender),
57       },
58       group: 'nodes'
59     });
60     nodeIds.add(connection.trim());
61   }
62
63   let interactionType = '';
64   let color = '#ccc';
65   if (row['Positive connections'] && row['Positive connections'].
includes(connection)) {
66     interactionType = 'positive';
67     color = getEdgeStyle('positive');
68   } else if (row['Negative connections'] && row['Negative connections
'].includes(connection)) {
69     interactionType = 'negative';
70     color = getEdgeStyle('negative');
71   } else if (row['Neutral'] && row['Neutral'].includes(connection)) {
72     interactionType = 'neutral';
73     color = getEdgeStyle('neutral');
74   } else if (row['Post mortem/supernatural'] && row['Post mortem/
supernatural'].includes(connection)) {
75     interactionType = 'supernatural';
76     color = getEdgeStyle('supernatural');
77   }
78
79   edges.push({
80     data: {
```

```
81     source: sourceNode,  
82     target: connection.trim(),  
83     interaction: interactionType,  
84     interactionColor: color,  
85     },  
86     group: 'edges',  
87   });  
88 });  
89 });  
90  
91 setElements([...nodes, ...edges]);  
92 };
```

Listing 6.2: JavaScript code for Network Building